

score

D9.1- Plan for exploitation and dissemination of the project results

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Approach
EC	European Commission
FP7	Seventh Framework Programme
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KMS	Knowledge Management Strategy
KO	Knowledge Output
KOQ	Knowledge Output Questionnaire
KOT	Knowledge Output Template
KT	Knowledge Transfer
KTP	Knowledge Transfer Plan
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Project Results
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

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BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Oarsoaldea, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

This deliverable is the updated version (M36) of the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PEDR), that was first submitted at M6 and then updated at M26 as part of Work Package 9 on dissemination, communication and exploitation. The PEDR provides the SCORE partners with guidelines on the different communication, dissemination and exploitation/knowledge transfer activities that are planned throughout the project, their schedule, partner responsibilities, as well as new and corrective actions that may be necessary to reach the pre-established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and to ensure appropriate impact of the action.

More specifically, the PEDR:

- Proposes a communication and dissemination policy and defines the objectives of the actions;
- Identifies the target audience for each objective or main result;
- Lists the communication and dissemination channels to be used for project promotion;
- Presents a schedule of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities throughout the project duration;
- Defines and monitors a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the success of the implementation (e.g., number of publications, size of the audience reached, number of visits on the website, etc.);
- Outlines the methodology that will be used to identify SCORE's exploitable outputs (or Key Exploitable Results);
- Identifies relevant (target/end) users, suitable transfer activities, and IP management;
- Identifies framework conditions and other factors influencing exploitation of the project's results;
- Identifies measures to ensure SCORE's longevity and legacy.

The document is drafted by Euronovia (WP9 leader) and ERINN (leader of the Knowledge management, transfer and exploitation of results), with inputs from all partners. The PEDR is an evolving document that is being updated throughout the project. Compared to the previous versions, this new revised version provides:

- An updated list of communication and dissemination activities, including a list of strategic congresses dealing with the main topic of the project that the consortium is planning to attend and an update on stakeholder engagement, with a specific focus on CCLs and local/regional stakeholders (Chapter 2).
- The list of prioritised KOs to date (as of June 2024) and the associated Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) that have been developed for those high prioritised KERs (Chapter 4).

This is the final update of the PEDR, while a final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities (D9.3) is planned at the end of the project (M48).

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

WP9 is a transversal work package integrating the results of all the WPs in the dissemination and exploitation process: it will ensure that the outputs and learnings arising from all the activities and all WPs of the project are visible to a wide audience and that these can be learned from and implemented on a European scale.

Figure 1: WP9 in relation to other WPs

WP9 is collaborating with all work packages to ensure sufficient and successful dissemination and exploitation.

Notably, WP9 is working particularly closely with WP2 across the tasks to ensure CDE activities are targeted to specific stakeholders and implemented to have optimal impact on local/regional stakeholders. As an essential aspect of WP9 knowledge transfer activities, further details are provided throughout.

WP9 activities are also linked with a number of other work packages and associated deliverables, as outlined below:

- **WP4:**
 - D4.1: *Citizen Science Playbook* (M48). This deliverable will report on **the stakeholders' networks built in each CCLL** as part of the WP2 activities to identify champions in each CCLL, which will be the SCORE ambassadors with the local communities. A list and analysis of the stakeholders prioritized in each CCLL is available in Annex 2 of this report.
 - D4.4: *Citizen science activities press-release* (M30). **Press releases and media actions** related to the various co-monitoring activities in CCLLs. These activities are mentioned under 2.4.10.2 of this report.
 - D4.5: *Citizen science activities in CCLLs* (M36). This deliverable presents a series of the **citizen science activities and workshops** that were carried out with the collaboration of WP2 in all the CCLLs. Some of these activities are mentioned under 2.4.11 of this report.

- **WP6:**
 - Task 6.5: Decision-support **guidelines for policy makers** (M30-44); closely linked with the knowledge transfer methodology and the update of residual coastal risk management guidelines by local/regional policymakers. A specific section on policy-makers considerations and engagement is available in 2.5.3 of this report.
- **WP7:**
 - D7.5: Policy guidelines aimed at different levels of governance, supported by evidence-based adaptation planning tools and use scenarios (M47). A set of **policy guidelines / policy briefs** (2-4 pages each) aimed at different levels of governance and policy making, and in a variety of coastal management contexts, containing evidence on coastal ecosystem services and their adaptation costs and benefits, as these have emerged from the SCORE project (especially its success stories). The guidelines will show and provide guidance on how public value is created out of adaptation measures designed and implemented in SCORE, and on how such measures can be supported and integrated in various governance levels (from local and regional to European). A summary of the first policy briefs published by the project is available in 2.4.10.3 of this report.
- **WP8:**
 - D8.10 (M24): *Early Warning and Spatial Digital Twin Assessment Plan* and D8.11 (M48): *Early Warning and Spatial Digital Twin Assessment Report*; links the **Impact Assessment** to the **knowledge transfer methodology** and developing the knowledge transfer plans for the Early Warning System and Digital Twin.
- **WP10:**
 - D10.2: *Networking and synergies between EU project (M48) is* - a report on the **networking and synergies with other EU projects**, which is also summarised in 2.4.12 of this report.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Definitions and terminology

The foundation of the SCORE PEDR is the knowledge management process which has been implemented from the start of the project and informs communication, dissemination, and exploitation. SCORE distinguishes between communication, dissemination, and exploitation (knowledge transfer), in line with the EC definitions below:

Communication is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting SCORE and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) SCORE and (ii) results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are for example a public website, social media, or a newsletter.

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protection or exploitation of results), including scientific publication in any medium. It is the process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (e.g., research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, enabling them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project. Tools and activities used for dissemination purposes are for example a public website, press releases, publications, and attendance of events.

Knowledge transfer and exploitation of results requires several steps including identifying exploitation mechanisms and activities. It focuses on identified end-users to ensure impact and uptake of the results. SCORE integrates diverse activities along the project lifetime to enhance the dissemination and exploitation strategy, maximize the expected impact and boost the project sustainability for the continuation of the project after EU-funding. The geographic coverage of the project also provides the foundation for a much broader engagement, and ultimately for the basis upon which to work towards the long-term sustainability of the project findings.

1.2. General rules and procedures

1.2.1. Communication within the SCORE consortium

Communication amongst partners is crucial to exchange up-to-date knowledge and data on what is going on in the different WPs and to enhance and optimise external communication and dissemination.

Internal communication is ensured through the regular exchange of information via e-mail, through the SCORE SharePoint and during regular meetings, when all partners gather to discuss achievements, upcoming activities, deadlines, and issues arising within the different work packages. WP leaders are also presenting main research advances during EB meetings or other WP leader meetings.

Communication and dissemination activities are coordinated by Euronovia, with the support of ERINN and ATU. **All partners regularly participate in communication and dissemination activities**, namely by:

- Communicating their activities and disseminating their results to their respective networks, on social media and through the production of news for the project website;
- Contributing to the content of the biannual newsletter (articles, interviews);

- Informing the other partners of interesting, related initiatives and events they could participate in;
- Keeping track of their communication and dissemination activities by filling in a dedicated reporting table available in the SharePoint of the project (see Annex 5);
- Disseminating results in open access publications, conferences, and relevant events.

In order to help CCLLs with communication and dissemination activities, ERINN provides support to the CCLLs, including the development of efficient communication and dissemination strategy (Annex 1). The involvement of all partners and CCLLs in the communication and dissemination activities ensures the project is more widely promoted to reach a wider audience and ultimately, to have a wider impact.

1.2.2. Use of graphic identity and EU visibility

A **common graphic identity** has been defined to allow for better visibility and recognition as well as branding of the SCORE project. Therefore, all dissemination tools and activities must refer to or include:

- The name of the project: SCORE
- The **URL of the project's website** (<https://score-eu-project.eu/>)
- The **SCORE project logo** (different versions to be used depending on the background colour)
- Information on EU funding** (as defined in Article 29.4 of the GA):
 - Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must: (a) display the EU emblem and (b) include the following text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534".
- When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem is given appropriate prominence.

1.2.3. Prior notice protocol

According to the Article 8.4.2 Dissemination of Own Results for all types of Publications, Dissemination and Communication Activities in the CA and Article 29.1 Obligation to disseminate results in the GA, where SCORE results are presented (including scientific publications, datasets, oral and poster presentations, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications), the Prior Notice Procedure must be applied as outlined below.

Euronovia tracks all prior notice messages received from the consortium and abstracts/associated documents received are stored in the SCORE SharePoint, easily accessible by all partners. A list can be provided to the EC upon request.

Prior Notice Procedure

A partner who intends to publish / present results, should:

- Submit the information (including full draft publication, or at least the abstract and where it will be submitted/presented) directly to the [Prior Notice](#) folder in SharePoint, **preferably latest 30 calendar days in advance of the activity for scientific publication and 15 calendar days for poster presentation** and **send email notification** to the WP9 leader (Euronovia) copying the project coordinator.
- WP9 leader Euronovia will subsequently immediately inform all partners by email.

- Partners have 25 days to object for scientific publication or 10 days in case of oral presentation** (in writing) sent to the lead author and WP9 leader, any objection needs to be justified and give precise modifications. An objection is justified if:
 - it adversely affects protection of results/background of the objecting party
 - legitimate interests of the objecting party would be significantly harmed
- If no objection is received before the set date, the author(s) can assume that there are no objections to the publication.
- Partners must ensure that the EU is acknowledged (correctly) and in the case of a scientific publication, whether it will be published in Open Access.

1.2.4. Open access to scientific publications

The SCORE partners are committed to **publishing scientific publications in open access**. The policy that will be implemented by the project will give priority to the Green model with the requirement to fix the embargo to 6 months after the first date of publication, as required by the EC. However, when not applicable, the publication policy of the consortium will be to pay the fees to make the scientific publications free of access. The costs related to paying the “Gold” open access for several publications have been integrated into the budget of the project.

The platform Sherpa/Romeo (<http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>) will be used to have a summary of permissions that are normally given as part of each publisher's copyright transfer agreement.

Further to this and whenever necessary, the addendum to the publication agreement provided by the European Commission (EC) will be used. This is an instrument that, if accepted by the editor, modifies the publisher's agreement, and allows the researcher to keep key rights to articles. The coordinator will support the researchers for these administrative issues related to the communication with the publishers.

In addition, the consortium will consider taking full advantage of the Open Research Europe platform (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu>) for any scientific publications issuing from research done within the project. This will enable the consortium to comply with open access obligations even after the project is ended and without any cost to the concerned beneficiaries.

All publications and accompanying data are stored in the **online project community created on Zenodo** within WP5: <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/>. All uploads are thus directly indexed in **OpenAIRE**.

1.2.5. Open access to scientific data

The project will collect relevant research data, that will be managed according to the Data Management Plan (D5.2, D5.5, D5.6). In accordance with the rules of the Open Research Data Pilot of which SCORE is a part of, for each research dataset, the SCORE partners will carefully study the possibility and pertinence to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). Data will be shared in accordance with recognized standards used in the research field, to maximize the opportunities for data linkage and interoperability. Sufficient metadata will be provided to enable the datasets to be used by others. Generally, the data being produced will be shared and made accessible for verification and re-use, according to the provisions foreseen in the CA. Access to specific data may be restricted under limited circumstances (e.g. for national security, to protect personal data and where the relevant new know-how acquired in the project is protected in order not to endanger the exploitation of the project's results). The first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) was delivered at M6 and an updated version was submitted in June 2023 (M24) Additional non-contractual updates were delivered throughout the whole duration of the project (M18, M30 and M36). Further updates are planned until the end of the project.

1.2.6. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Rules regarding intellectual property rights are exposed in the Consortium Agreement. As a general principle, the knowledge generated by the project remains the ownership of the team(s) who produced the results. This section outlines a brief summary of some key aspects of the rights and obligations relating to the protection of these results, but this is not an exhaustive summary. For further details on project and H2020 rules surrounding ownership and protection of results please refer to the Grant Agreement (GA), Consortium Agreement (CA) and the Data Management Plan (DMP – D5.2).

Ownership of Results

Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them. Two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or separate them, for the purpose of applying for, obtaining, or maintaining their protection (GA Article 26). The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (joint ownership agreement), to ensure compliance with their obligations under the GA. If valuable results are not protected, the Commission may under certain circumstances assume ownership of the results (see GA Article 26 for further details).

Protection of Results

Each beneficiary has an obligation to protect its results. For any results that can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited, beneficiaries must examine the possibility of protecting them and if possible, protect them even if this requires further research and development or private investment. If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, to stop protecting them or not seek an extension of protection, the EU may under certain conditions (GA Article 26.4) assume ownership to ensure their (continued) protection.

Exploitation of Results

Each beneficiary has an obligation to exploit its results. They must, up to four years after the period set out in GA Article 3, take measures aiming to ensure exploitation of its results by: using them in further research activities; developing, creating, or marketing a product or process; creating and providing a service, or using them in standardisation activities (see GA Article 28). If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced in accordance with GA Article 43.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) & Management

The SCORE CA follows the standard rules as outlined in the Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement (DESCA, www.desca-2020.eu) model for Horizon 2020, which defines the main approach regarding the ownership, protection, and access to key knowledge like intellectual property rights (IPR) and data. The objective is to ensure fair and transparent manners for exploiting and protecting the background information and the foreground results. This allows SCORE to pursue market opportunities arising collectively and individually from the project's results. SCORE follows the rules for IP set out by the EC, as regulated, and agreed upon by all partners in the CA.

More information can be found in GA Section 3 (Article 23a) "Management of Intellectual Property"; Subsection 2 (Article 24) "Rights and Obligations Related to Background"; Subsection 3 (Article 26) "Rights and Obligations related to Results".

SCORE has established an **Innovation Board**, chaired by MBI and consisting of the project coordinator and all project SMEs. The committee supports IPR protection and ensures that effective protocols are established and adhered to for the management of IP during knowledge transfer and dissemination activities. All Key Exploitable Results (KERs) produced during the project are assessed for the need of IPR protection through the Innovation Board, which will

discuss strategic issues, ethics, and the exploitation of results. The partners ensure that adequate steps towards protection are taken prior to exploitation, dissemination, and communication, preventing unapproved public disclosure of results, tools, products and services.

2.COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OVERVIEW

2.1. Phases

The planning and execution of the project dissemination activities requires a schedule closely aligned with key project deliverables and milestones. At this scope, the project is organised around 3 phases:

- **Initial awareness phase (Month 0-12)** to ensure the project is known to relevant stakeholders and the public in general. In this phase, we developed the project website and various communication and dissemination materials, including the project graphical identity (i.e., project logo, branding guidelines, templates for project documents and presentations). In this phase, we also did an initial mapping key stakeholders to be included in the project database to optimize targeted communication and dissemination, that is regularly updated. *This phase has been achieved.*
- **Targeted dissemination phase (Month 12-36)** to encourage a better understanding of the project results leading to greater engagement of external stakeholders and better future uptake of the project outcomes. To do so, we not only disseminated project results but also success stories showing how public value is created out of adaptation measures in SCORE. In this phase, the consortium enriched the website and social media channels with new content. SCORE's knowledge was collected and analysed by relevant partners on the IB. As such, initial Knowledge Transfer Plan and targeted dissemination action were identified and planned, this includes showcasing preliminary project results to the target audiences through scientific publications, organisation of workshops and webinars and participation in relevant conferences through oral and poster presentations as well as project booths. Impact assessment was crucial at this stage to monitor and reorientate the strategy, when necessary (e.g., increase our video content, organise more regular webinars, offer new content on our website, identify and use additional dissemination venues). The mid-term analysis is available in deliverable D9.2 submitted in June 2023, while an update of the KPIs analysis at M36 is available in section 2.7 and in Annex 6 of this deliverable. In this phase, we also started to map the project exploitable results and defined first knowledge transfer plans, as detailed in chapter 5. *This phase has been achieved.*
- **Presentation of results (Month 36-48):** This represents the period just prior to the end of the project when the project reaches its most significant outputs. This is the most active period in the whole PEDR strategy, matching with the finalisation of the project and the publications of the final project results. Several dissemination materials and activities are planned in the last year, in particular: a final brochure, a final media press kit, the participation of project partners in several external events, publication of scientific papers and other articles, policy briefs, and the organisation of a final infoday. Exploitation of results will also be ensured by outlining the actions required to fulfil their potential. Final Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) will be mapped, detailing customized transfer activities for the (target/end) user. This will contribute to maximizing the project's impact and legacy on a large range of stakeholders. *This is the current phase.*

Table 1 below presents more in detail the main tasks planned within the dissemination and knowledge transfer strategy over the 4 years of the project.

Table 1: Dissemination and exploitation strategy planning

Main Tasks	Task description	Year 1	2	3	4
Dissemination and exploitation strategy definition	During the first months of the project, the consortium defined the dissemination and exploitation strategies focusing on the planned project outcomes and targeted stakeholders. This strategy is annually monitored: corrections are made, and new activities are implemented, if needed, to meet the KPIs defined in the GA.				
Mapping and clustering with stakeholders' network	SCORE is developing a contact database consisting of the stakeholders, potential end-users, partners and other external actors in the field that are being targeted in the project. This started at the beginning of the project. CCLs and partners are using their own networks of contact at the local level to make sure relevant people are reached and involved in SCORE activities.				
Targeted dissemination	Participation in events and scientific conferences, scientific publications, organization of workshops, creation of communication materials, media general outreach through press releases and articles in magazines.				
Exploitation	Mapping of key exploitable results, implementation of exploitation strategy focusing on the adoption of project outcomes and directing further development of results beyond the project.				
Impact Assessment	Assess the project outcomes impacts with direct feedback; Stakeholder validated project outcomes.				
Intensive dissemination and Knowledge Transfer period	This final period will match with the finalization of the project and the publications of the final project results, resulting in an intensive dissemination and knowledge management strategy.				

2.2. Target groups

The consortium has identified several groups that have an interest and/or will be affected by the SCORE project. These are being targeted by different communication and dissemination actions and networking/clustering activities, as detailed in the table below. Targeted audiences are being refined throughout the lifetime of the project in relation to the various activities developed within the different work packages.

Table 2: Summary of target groups, objectives and content for SCORE dissemination

Target and user groups	Description of the target groups and dissemination objectives	Objectives	Dissemination content and channels
Academic and research and development community	This group targets all research communities interested in the project's developments, results and innovation which can be beneficiary for their own research activities: climate model experts, climate scientists and other environmental scientists, engineers, and social scientists (outreach experts).	Transfer of knowledge, raise awareness, reuse of the scientific data, get support from the scientific community, boost the project sustainability through the development	Public deliverables, scientific publications, conferences, webinars, and other scientific events.

		of new related research projects.	
Cities	<p>This group, targets all the important political and technical actors in European coastal cities (and not only from countries of the consortium):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Policy/Governance: Chambers of Commerce, City Councils, local / regional politicians ▪ Communities: general public, local citizens ▪ Housing, planning authorities ▪ Other coastal cities 	Increase the replicability of the CCLL results obtained in the project to other cities, transfer of knowledge and dissemination of the processes.	Public deliverables, targeted dissemination activities and conferences, webinars, workshops at the local level, open innovation events.
Industrial sector	<p>The project is of relevance for organizations in various sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate technology, weather station/ sensor manufacturers, software developers ▪ Civil Engineers, planners ▪ Insurance companies 	Demonstrate the business potential; push towards adoption of SCORE products and services; collect feedback on expectations and requirement to adjust commercial exploitation plans; convince about the technical feasibility and competitiveness of concept and tools developed.	Techno-economic assessment, LCA, dedicated workshops, public deliverables, scientific publications, webinars, related project events and exhibition in trade fairs.
Government bodies and policy makers	This is a wide group encompassing innovation driven local, regional, national authorities, representatives & associations, Ministries, parliaments and national & international Public Administrations.	Demonstrate the benefits of SCORE concept and tools to reach the EU goals, raise awareness about proposed regulatory evolution in SCORE.	Final recommendation in deliverables, policy briefs, press kit, participation in policy events.
European and international networks and European Technology clusters	This group refers to activities addressing external task forces & relevant European technology clusters (e.g. Ocean and Climate Platform, the European Climate Adaptation Platform Climate-ADAPT, Coastal list, Green Deal Projects Support Office Network of Multipliers, 3D grupa, Aclima-Basque Environment Cluster - Asociación Cluster de Industrias de Medio Ambiente de Euskadi, etc.)	Use as dissemination relays towards their members.	Public deliverables, press kit, articles, press releases, event announcements, webinars, communication package.
EU projects and networks working in similar domain	The participation of project partners in other relevant projects offers the opportunity to establish quick links among parties through joint actions. Joint dissemination actions will also be implemented with similar projects in the framework of the Horizon Result Booster and through the Network of Multipliers of the Green Deal Projects Support Office (GD-SO).	Coordinate dissemination activities to maximize their impact, exchange on R&D results to improve robustness of project results.	Dissemination events, conferences and booths, participation in workshops and webinars, joint newsletters, joint dissemination on social media, etc.
The general public	The general public consists of a general audience and other actors not identified as direct targeted	To raise awareness on the importance of the SCORE	Project website, brochure, press releases,

	groups by the project, though this group can have strong interest in the project: citizen Interest Groups, NGOs, Community Action Groups, students, etc.	topic for the future and inform about the benefits of the project towards a resilient society.	social media, popularization events, citizen science initiatives, videos, interviews, etc.
North Sea region's cities and municipalities	The project will target the North Sea region's cities to enhance the replication of SCORE activities.	Demonstrate the benefits of SCORE concept and tools to reach the EU goals. Also, transfer of knowledge and replicate solutions.	Invitation to SCORE events and webinars, invitations to participate in joint activities, policy briefs, final recommendations in deliverables.

2.3. SCORE messages

The SCORE communication, dissemination and knowledge transfer activities are tailored to ensure that important messages are widespread to the adequate targeted audience and that the public at large gets connected with SCORE.

The **main objectives of the dissemination and knowledge transfer activities** is to maximize impact of the project through:

- Showing how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible**, notably in achieving scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness and solving societal challenges.
- Showing how the outcomes are relevant to people's everyday lives**, by creating jobs, introducing novel technologies, or enhancing the quality of life of EU citizens and better protecting the environment.
- Making better use of results**, by ensuring they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policymaking and by industry and the scientific community to ensure a follow-up of the development of the technology.
- Establishing the dialogue with stakeholders** to achieve the SCORE objectives, as stakeholder engagement is a two-way process.

Also, for each different audience identified, a distinct strategy using targeted messages, means and language is being used. For each audience we are trying to answer the following questions and adapt the message we are delivering:

- Why do they need to know?
- What makes the issue urgent?
- What are the consequences if no action is taken?
- What solutions are we offering?
- How does our work relate to everyday life?
- Does it link to any broader societal issue?

Rather than focusing only on the provision of factual information, we are trying as much as possible to position our research topic within a broader socio-economic and policy context, so that it is easier to explain the results and their relevance to both policymakers and citizens.

Below are some **key messages** that we are delivering through the dissemination activities. In addition to these overarching messages, specific key messages per target group are developed for each of SCORE's Key Exploitable Results as part of the Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) to support tailored knowledge transfer (see Chapter 4.1).

- The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. SCORE is enhancing the role of coastal cities in local climate resilience, demonstrating positive impacts of project solutions, showing project development/updates on the implementation of the CCLL framework for replication in other cities.
- Although all CCLLs have different environmental and geographical conditions, they face similar challenges as shown by the hazards they experience (i.e., coastal and inland flooding, coastal erosion and coastal storm surge). The potential sectoral impacts of these risks are also similar: risk to tourism, loss of cultural heritage, damage to commercial and residential buildings, damage to energy networks, agricultural stress, loss of wetlands, loss of animal habitat, damage to civil infrastructure, and risk to the local economy.
- Citizens, public authorities, and key users have an essential role in co-creating and co-designing solutions to address climate change, together with scientists, researchers and engineers. This will ensure solutions are sustainable and acceptable to society.
- An Ecosystem Based Approach (EBA) makes use of biodiversity and ecosystem services as part of an overall strategy to adapt to the adverse effects of climate change and increase resilience. SCORE is developing and delivering a new generation of tools and methodologies, as well as validated EBAs, to enhance climate resilience in European coastal cities and settlements through the adaptation to sea level rise and extreme events risks. This provides an opportunity for further testing and development of innovative tools and methodologies for enhancing climate resilience in other areas.
- New tools and recommendations are needed to improve the long-term climate resilience of coastal cities. SCORE is contributing to this need with targeted policy briefs, a digital twin platform, an early warning support system, citizen science activities, EbA catalogue, a co-creation toolkit, geosurveys, and online courses.

2.4. Tools, materials and activities

To reach the SCORE objectives and to ensure proper visibility and impact, different tools and materials are planned, as detailed in the Description of Work and summarised in the Table 3 below.

Table 3: Main elements of the communication and dissemination strategy

Visual Identity	The project branding helps all partners communicate about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner. The project branding includes project logo, visual identity , written identity including tagline and key messages and templates for Word and PowerPoint.
Communication materials	A communication package (M6) containing the main elements of the project is available as: a PPT presentation, poster, roll-up banner and a Word document (one-page project description, objectives, impacts) including logo, visual identity materials and templates. - 1 flyer (M6), 1 final brochure (M48), 1 timeline infography (M12), 1 motion design video promoted through the EU audiovisual channels and YouTube (M33), Partners interviews (M36) will be integrated into video for wide online dissemination - Liaise with the different partners' communication departments for wider dissemination of these materials using the partners' existing communication channels
Website	The public website contains information targeted for the general public (description of the project, the WPs, the partners, basic information on the technology) as well as specific information targeted

	towards the different types of stakeholders linked to the project (training materials, scientific papers, environmental impact).
Social networks and online presence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social web-based media (creation of 1 LinkedIn page, 1 Facebook page, 1 Instagram account and 1 Twitter account) targets the general audience as well as more technology related stakeholders - All project partners regularly re-share content from their personal and institutional social media accounts to direct their audience to SCORE's channels and website, following an agreed-upon schedule. In doing so, the consortium will reap the benefits of the partners' combined audience base, while building a strong brand that is able to live beyond the 4-year project and thus have an extended impact on cultural heritage transformation. By adding relevant hashtags (such as #H2020, #EBA) SCORE's reach is further amplified.
Press relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 2 press releases (M6 and M42) and 1 final media press kit to be done at the end of the project and disseminated to the press - 8 newsletters (every 6 months), - Public relations and media coverage (national/international press, communication to citizens and authorities). EUR will manage these actions in partnership with the press department of the partners. - 2 articles in specialized magazines (Y3 and Y4)
Scientific publications	30 scientific publications in science, industry and social science journals to widely disseminate the project outcomes and results.
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of several events: training schools, workshops, webinars and one final infoday targeted at the general public and other non-experts - Participation in external events and scientific conferences to present the project activities and outcomes. - At least 1 participation/exhibition in science popularization events, the EU researcher's night, the national science festivals existing in the partner countries

In the following paragraphs is a brief description of the tools, material and activities which have been prepared or are planned to be prepared in the next months to ensure effective communication and knowledge transfer of project results. *For a more complete description of tools and materials created and used during the period M1-M24, see the mid-term report on communication and dissemination activities (D9.2). A more detailed description of tools and materials created and used during the period M24-M48 will be provided in the Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities (D9.3).*

2.4.1. Visual identity

The project branding, created right at the start of the project, is helping all partners to communicate about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner: it includes the project logo, project identity and style guide, templates for Word and PowerPoint documents.

- The **SCORE logo** consists of a clear and modern font and of an icon representing a wave composed of different shades of blue. This icon symbolizes both the water element typical of the coastal cities as well as the specific challenges tackled by the project, such as the increase of sea levels, coastal erosion, and extreme weather events. This logo will be used in all communications (written deliverables, journal papers, presentations, invitations etc.) to ensure project recognition and visibility.

The project logo and symbol are available for download on the project dedicated space in the SharePoint platform, with access restricted to project partners.

Specific guidelines on how to use the logo both on a white and dark background, as well as indications on its placement, font and colours have been described in a specific brand manual created in the first months of the project.

- The **project's graphical identity** includes fonts, colours and texts directly derived from the project logotype. Such visual identity is defined by the project logo and is being used in all dissemination tools and printed materials. For more detailed information on the project graphical identity, please see [deliverable D9.5](#).

Figure 2: SCORE project logo

- **Templates for the project deliverables**, meeting agenda and minutes have also been produced during the first months of the project, together with a PowerPoint template to be used by the partners for all presentations on SCORE both in internal and external events.

Figure 3: Power Point template

Figure 4: Deliverable template

The deliverable template consists of two pages. The left page is a cover page with a blue background and a circular graphic. It features the SCORE logo, the title 'DX.N-Title of document', and fields for 'DATE OF DELIVERY - DD/MM/YYYY', 'AUTHOR(S) - NAME(S)', and 'INSTITUTION/COMPANY NAME'. The right page is a metadata page with a white background and a blue header. It contains two main sections: 'DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS' and 'VERSION MANAGEMENT'. The 'DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS' section includes a table with fields for Project acronym (SCORE), Project title (Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities), Starting date (01.07.2021), Duration (48 months), Call identifier (H2020-LC-CLA-2020-2), and Grant Agreement no (101003534). The 'VERSION MANAGEMENT' section includes a table with columns for Version, Name, Date, and Description, showing versions V 0.1 to V 1.0. At the bottom, there is a disclaimer: 'All information in this document only reflects the author's view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.' The footer includes 'SCORE_Dx.n_Version number' and '2/12'.

Figure 5: Agenda and meeting minutes template

The agenda and meeting minutes template consists of three pages. The left page is a cover page for the agenda, featuring the SCORE logo, the title 'Name of the project meeting', and fields for 'DATE OF THE MEETING' and 'PLACE OF THE MEETING'. The middle page is the agenda itself, showing a schedule for two days: 'TUESDAY 24 AUGUST 2021, 13.30 – 17.00' and 'WEDNESDAY 25 AUGUST 2021, 13.30 – 17.00'. Each day includes a table of activities with times and descriptions, such as 'EXECUTIVE BOARD MEETING' and 'WP3 30 min Presentation + 25 min Q&A'. The right page is a meeting minutes cover page, featuring the SCORE logo, the title 'Meeting minutes', and fields for 'DATE - DD/MM/YYYY', 'PLACE - Web meeting or place', 'AUTHOR(S) - Name(s)', and 'INSTITUTION/COMPANY NAME'. The right page also includes a 'DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS' section with a table for identification and SCORE, and a 'VERSION MANAGEMENT' section with a table for version details. The footer includes 'Title of document - SCORE_[Meeting name] minutes' and '2/6'.

2.4.2. One page project description/ Information sheet

An information sheet/consent form translated into different languages was prepared by ATU at the start of the project for distribution to participants in any project-related activity where necessary (scientific research, user requirements and socio-economic studies, and system testing). This document contains a simple description of the SCORE project and its objectives, as well as a Consent Form that participants will be requested to sign, in some cases, before the start of specific research activities.

2.4.3. Flyer and brochure

A project **flyer** with general information on the project and the 10 CCLLs was created by Euronovia at M6. This has been distributed to partners for use at external events that the consortium is organizing or attending.

A **brochure** will be created by Euronovia at the end of the project (M47-48) to present the main results and achievements of the project. It will be distributed through the project contact database, the website, social networks, and during the final infoday.

2.4.4. Poster and roll-up banner

A project **poster** and **roll-up banner** have been prepared by Euronovia and are being used during external conferences and events attended by the consortium to promote and present the results arising from the project.

2.4.5. Infographics

1 timeline infographic illustrating the project's key activities was designed and published by Euronovia through the SCORE channels in July 2022. This infographic is regularly shared on social media to show the progress of the project according to its timeline.

Additional infographics were developed by ERINN, with support of the CCLLs and WP7 (Figure 6), in their relevant local languages, to illustrate the main hazards they are facing and the EBA that were selected as solutions to better protect them. These were developed to support the knowledge transfer of the MCA process with local stakeholders, in particular those stakeholders who attended the CCLL collaboration sessions to highlight the results of the session and the ongoing work in the CCLL. These were developed in coordination with KO 7.2. To overcome language barriers, communication and dissemination materials are consistently translated into the local language, facilitating the transmission of key messages.

Figure 6: SCORE CCLLs infographics regarding prioritised EBAs.

UCD has developed a catalogue of infographics templates that the CCLLs can utilise to share the outputs from the CCLLs, including research results across the technical work packages, to disseminate key messages in a simple and digestible form for their stakeholders. They can either be shared on social media, sent alongside a policy brief as a concise explanation, shared with colleagues prior to meetings to set the scene, amongst many others.

These strategies are implemented alongside the CCLLs activities and workshops with the support of the Innovation Board, to ensure the continual engagement of stakeholders and citizens in SCORE activities.

Figure 7: Infographic Templates to promote EBA Selection & Implementation

2.4.6. Audio-visual material and YouTube channel

Different types of audio-visual materials are planned during the project duration. Videos are posted on the SCORE YouTube channel and promoted on social media. The following audio-visual materials have been created so far:

- A [SCORE presentation video](#) and [a podcast](#) were produced by ATU at the start of the project.
- A [video message](#) was recorded by the Irish Minister for Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, Mr Simon Harris to support the launch of the project and displayed to all partners during the SCORE Kick-off meeting. *See the mid-term report (D9.2) for more details.*
- A **video** presenting the project activities and tools in an attractive and dynamic way was produced by Euronovia and published in March 2024 (M33). While the voice-over of the video is in English, subtitles are available in all the nine languages of the partners (English, Spanish, Basque, Catalan, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Slovene and Turkish).
- 10 **partner interviews** have been posted online, including interviews of members of the CCLLs in different languages. Interviews are recorded by Euronovia during consortium meetings or during events attended by partners.
- The recordings of the 10 SCORE **webinars** organised from March 2022 to May 2024 to present the main outcomes from each Work Package are available in the SCORE YouTube Channel.
- Short **promotional videos** illustrating the 'Behind the scenes' of partners' participation to internal and external events were created and disseminated online by Euronovia;
- Videos illustrating the **Minecraft workshops** and activities performed under Task 9.6 were developed by UCD and posted online. As an example, short videos were produced and disseminated online to promote the Minecraft workshop organized online on 7 June 2023 as part of the EU Green Week (see for example: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072153643923185664> and

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7069243553868083200>). The game was also livestreamed for 6 hours on the SCORE YouTube channel for people to follow the players' quest and discover the SCORE Minecraft world. Short promotional videos of the Minecraft activities were also disseminated on social media to promote the second edition of the SCORE Training School in March 2024 (<https://score-eu-project.eu/2024/05/14/a-look-back-at-the-2nd-edition-of-the-score-training-school/>).

- 2 SCORE's Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) (Task 9.6.3) were developed by ERINN and made available to the public (<https://score-eu-project.eu/online-courses/>). The MOOC is an open-online course for which participants from around the world can learn about a SCORE and our associated themes (i.e., EBAs, living labs, etc.), utilising a variety of mediums, including videos selected from the EBA Training Schools sessions and the webinars. The utilisation of SCORE's MOOC will enable the project to reach a wider audience and provide valuable climate action skills/learnings to citizens in Europe and worldwide.
- IHS with the support of ERINN and the Innovation Board have developed a "[How-To](#)" video for the Co-create your City Toolkit (KO2.1) which is being highlighted in the Horizon Results Platform.

In the final year of the project, we are planning to produce additional audio-video materials, as follows:

- New video interviews of partners to present the experiences and best practices (as well as difficulties encountered) from the CCLLs involved in the project;
- New videos illustrating the activities performed under Task 9.6 will be developed by UCD and posted online on the occasion of the next edition of the EbA Training School planned in early 2025;
- New MOOCs, which are currently under development by ERINN;
- Short promotional videos illustrating the consortium participation and main contributions to future events;
- When relevant, new videos to support the utilisation of SCORE's Knowledge Outputs (see Chapter 4) will be posted on the Horizon Results Platform.

2.4.7. Website

The project website (<https://score-eu-project.eu>) is of crucial importance to enhance the visibility of SCORE, as it serves as the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project activities, deliverables, and outcomes.

Together with social media, the website is a key tool for reaching out to a wide audience, communicate about the project and its results. The website provides essential information on the project, such as its concept and objectives, workplan, partners, activities, technology to be developed, information on the CCLLs, news, publications, and more.

The website was launched by Euronovia in two phases: a one-page version of the website was created and published online in October 2021, while the full version of the website, including several pages, was published in December 2021. More information on the content and structure of the website can be found in deliverable D9.6.

The website is regularly updated, with new content regarding each CCLLs, news articles, deliverables, publications, and other resources. Regarding news articles, 100 have already been published out of the 96 planned for the whole project duration. Due to the number of news article, it was decided to move the news related to scientific publications to [a new page](#) to facilitate access and ensure users can easily find the information they are looking for. Lastly, additional pages were created to increase the dissemination of key project results:

- "Tools and platforms" which lists and provides information about the different tools and platforms developed by the project and made available to the public

- “Other publications” which gathers all the SCORE policy briefs as well as other key reports in which SCORE is referenced.

Figure 8: Homepage of the SCORE website

Since June 2024 the SCORE website now offers several accessibility tools: it is now possible to increase or decrease the size of the text, apply grayscale or higher contrast, and more options. This feature is visible on the left-hand side of the screen where a blue square with a person is visible.

An important metrics to monitor for the website is the geographical coverage in order to evaluate if we have a good balance between users from the countries of our CCLLs and users from other places. At M36, the countries with CCLLs (Ireland, Spain, Portugal, Italy, Slovenia, Poland, and Turkey) account for 40% of all users which is a very satisfactory number proving that we are reaching the right locations as well as gathering interest from additional places (in particular the United States, the Netherlands, France, and the United Kingdom).

See the mid-term report (D9.2) for more details and statistics on the website during the first half of the project. Detailed statistics for the period M24-M48 will be provided in D9.3.

2.4.8. Geostories

During the October 2023 Innovation Board Meeting, following analysis of Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) for several Knowledge Outputs (KOs), WP9 and the Innovation Board determined that a centralised dissemination resource for the CCLLs would be necessary to reach more local target users. As such, specific dissemination materials on the SCORE Platform have been developed to support targeted outreach to local and regional stakeholders.

Partners from WP9 and WP5 have co-developed with each CCLL a GeoStory on the SCORE Platform about the work going on in their lab. These GeoStories, intentionally designed for easy navigation, showcase SCORE activities and results tailored to a CCLL’s local stakeholders on a single webpage. Acting as a centralized highlight reel, they allow readers to view the most relevant and beneficial projects and activities in their area. See below examples of CCLL GeoStories highlighting local activities and outputs – such as the hazard maps in Massa (Figure 9), citizen science activities in Piran (Figure 10) and sensor deployment in Oeiras (Figure 11).

To co-create these GeoStories, ERINN developed templates to collect information and activities that were most impactful in each CCLL. Additionally, published deliverables, articles, policy briefs, and KOs were assessed for relevant resources for each CCLL. The ERINN and WP5 teams then compiled this information into an online starting template, from which CCLLs could then adjust and manage as their own GeoStories.

The GeoStories are intended to be dynamic resources, with additional elements (activities, outputs, etc.) being periodically added throughout the duration of the project. Each CCLL team has included the most relevant and interesting activities and outputs for local stakeholders, including citizens, local policymakers, and public administrators. To ensure accessibility, the GeoStories are developed in the local languages of the CCLLs. The GeoStories will be continuously shared with engaged stakeholders at events, activities, and on social media platforms.

Figure 9: Hazard maps developed in WP1 as displayed in the Massa CCLL Geostory

Figure 10: The Piran CCLL has displayed their most impactful citizen engagement activities in their GeoStories as a GeoCarousel, making it interactive for readers.

Figure 11: The Oeiras CCLL has described and displayed information about their sensor deployment activities in their municipality on their GeoStory

The most recent iterations of these GeoStories can be found here: platform.score-eu-project.eu. A link to each one of the Geostories is included in the CCLL individual pages on the SCORE website.

2.4.9. Social media

Social media are being used by the consortium to inform and connect with professionals, policymakers, and the scientific community as well as to reach out to the general public (students, citizens, local communities).

A [LinkedIn page](#) and a [Twitter account](#) were created before the start of the project, in June 2021, in order to inform researchers, stakeholders and similar EU projects of the launch of the project:

- The **LinkedIn** account is managed by Euronovia and ATU with the aim to disseminate official project information among a professional audience. Partners and CCLLs regularly contributes to write posts on LinkedIn using their personal/institutional LinkedIn accounts: this way they will be able to raise awareness of the project among their contact networks and the consortium will reap the benefits of the partners' combined networks to reach a wider audience. The account currently has **1243 followers**.
- The **Twitter** account is managed by Euronovia, ERINN and ATU in a more informal way, especially to retweet partners and tweets coming from CCLLs' members to keep the followers updated on the work undertaken daily by each partner. The account currently has **425 followers**.

Figure 12: LinkedIn and Twitter accounts

A [Facebook page](#) and an [Instagram account](#) were created by Euronovia in September and October 2021 respectively to primarily target students and the general public, with content focused on educating the public on climate change and its effects on coastal cities:

- The **Instagram** account is run by each CCLL for 1 week/month on a rotational basis: they publish stories and posts to show their work within the project. The account currently has **250 followers**.
- The **Facebook** page is managed by Euronovia, ERINN and ATU who feed it by reposting relevant LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram publications from partners and CCLLs. The page currently has **167 followers**.

Figure 13: Facebook and Instagram accounts

The different social media accounts contribute to the continuous development of a community of people interested in how the project is tackling climate change and its effects on coastal cities, and to raising awareness on the project and its objectives while allowing for more interaction with related initiatives.

SCORE has developed a **social media strategy** which involves the contributions of all SCORE partners and members responsible for each CCLL to ensure an efficient and coordinated contribution from all the consortium to ensure maximal impact and that KPI targets are met.

- Partners are using their own institutional and personal accounts to share any news and updates on the activities developed within SCORE, to use pictures and hashtags and tag the SCORE project so that we can share the information on the official project accounts. To have a greater impact on local stakeholders, partners are also posting news in their native language. At M36, at least 405 posts have been published on the partners' social media accounts;
- We have identified at the start of the project (and regularly updated) a list of similar projects whose followers could be interested in SCORE activities: we followed these accounts to increase the chances to be followed back, so that they receive our news in their profile;
- News and updates are regularly posted on the SCORE official accounts, using key hashtags, pictures and videos, and tagging partners as well relevant accounts to increase visibility as much as possible.
- Following the impact analysis performed at M24, we decided to increase our video content (especially for Instagram with the Reels feature) to gain more visibility.

The **impact of the SCORE social media accounts is regularly monitored** by using the different social media statistic tools:

- Statistics on the use of Twitter were analysed through Twitter Analytics which, as of June 2024, is no longer available for free
- Facebook Insights provides useful information on how the content is resonating with the audience, how the page is growing and performing;
- Statistics of the LinkedIn page is accessible by the page administrators;
- Statistics for Instagram are available through the Instagram business feature;

*A complete social media impact analysis **for the first half of the project** is provided in the mid-term report (D9.2). A KPI analysis updated at M36 is available in Annex 6.*

2.4.10. Publications

2.4.10.1. Newsletters

8 newsletters (twice a year) are planned to be sent out to the newsletter subscribers during the duration of the project. 5 newsletters have already been sent out to the list of subscribers in January and July 2022, January and July 2023, January 2024. Newsletters are available on the project website (<https://score-eu-project.eu/newsletter/>) and have been disseminated on social media, as well as sent by e-mail to relevant networks of project partners to increase the size of the dissemination list, which at M36 includes 568 contacts.

The next newsletters are planned to be sent out in July 2024, January 2025 and June 2025.

2.4.10.2. Press relations and media coverage

Important efforts are dedicated to press relations in order to ensure a good media coverage about the SCORE project, both at the European/National level and at the local/regional CCLL level:

- **2 press releases** have been published by ATU since the start of the project: in July 2021 to officially communicate the launch of the project (this was translated into French and Italian and distributed by the project partners to their contact networks and widely published through their institutional websites and social networks. ATU also sent their press release to all regional press in the Northwest of Ireland); in March 2024 to communicate about the different citizen science activities in place to involve local communities in innovative co-warning and co-monitoring activities for improving resilience to extreme weather events. The full document is available at this link: https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/SCORE_Press-release-SCORE-innovative-citizen-science-activities-to-tackle-climate-change-in-coastal-areas.pdf.
- UCD and ATU published a press release about the citizen science activity “Smart Pebbles” in their CCLLs (<https://lero.ie/news-and-events/news/dublin-and-sligo-students-release-%E2%80%98smart%E2%80%99-pebbles-track-climate-change-impacts>)
- Oarsoaldea sent out a press release in June 2023 about the first EBA training school (<https://oarsoaldea.hitza.eus/2023/06/02/klima-egokitzapena-lantzeko-hiru-egun-antolatu-dituzte/>)
- 95 **media appearances** including videos and interviews broadcast by local and regional TV and radio channels have been recorded since the start of the project, including:
 - **3 articles** have been published in the SiliconRepublic Irish, a **specialized magazine** for science and technology news: one in August 2021 about the project launch, one in September 2023 about the "smart pebbles" activity to track coastal erosion and one in April 2024 on SCORE citizen science activities.

In addition to the publications and media appearances cited above, the SCORE consortium is regularly looking for opportunities to be featured in external online blog articles and reports, also in collaboration with other similar EU projects. See 2.5.4 of the mid-term report (D9.2) for further details.

A **final media press kit** along a **final press release** will be prepared at the end of the project for massive dissemination of the project final outcomes. Further efforts will be made in the final year to target European-level specialised magazine (such as the Green European Journal, the Ecologist, Revolve, The Mayor.eu) to disseminate the results of the project to a wider audience.

2.4.10.3. Policy briefs

5 policy briefs have been published by the SCORE consortium since the start of the project: 3 relevant at the European level and 2 targeting local policy-makers in two CCLLs:

- When will a 2-meter rise in sea level occur, and how might we adapt?
- ADAPT4COAST - Integrated strategies for climate resilience in EU coastal cities
- Joint Policy Recommendations on Climate Adaptation from European Coastal Cities
- Building Climate Resilience in Sligo County through Ecosystem-based Adaptation, Smart Technologies, and Coastal City Living Lab
- Heatwaves in Portugal: Understanding, Mitigation, Adaptation

These policy briefs are available for download on the SCORE website: <https://score-eu-project.eu/other-publications/>. While all policy briefs are promoted online and disseminated widely through the SCORE newsletter, by project partners to their networks, at events and through other EU projects, local policy briefs are being disseminated locally, targeting in particular local policy makers. As an example, the policy brief relevant for Sligo was presented to the Sligo County Council.

A brief focused on “Adapting to sea level rise - Reshaping the future of our coastal cities: Enhancing Coastal Cities’ Resilience through Nature-Based Solutions” is currently being developed in collaboration with the [Ocean and Climate Platform](#), following the participation of SCORE partners in an online workshop on NbS in April 2024. This brief aims to provide guidance to decision-makers on how to overcome the typical challenges of integrating NbS into adaptation strategies for coastal cities. It will be distributed through the Ocean & Climate Platform gathering more than 100 members – research institutes, NGOs, aquariums, private sector, French institutions and international agencies, local authorities – as well as through the SCORE partners’ networks.

Lastly, in the project’s final year, Task 7.5 will focus on developing and issuing policy recommendations to assist decision-making in climate change adaptation at local, national and EU levels. Starting in July 2024, this task will culminate in deliverable D7.5 in June 2025. This deliverable will present a set of policy guidelines tailored to various governance levels and coastal management contexts, demonstrating how public value is generated from adaptation measures designed and implemented in the SCORE project. Additionally, within Task 6.5, a set of guidelines for the management of residual coastal risk is planned to assist coastal city decision-makers in designing a strategy based on the set of financial and structural interventions available to them, tailored to the specific characteristics of their city. WP9 will work with WP7 and WP6 to facilitate dissemination of these policy briefs to appropriate stakeholders. Dissemination will have a prominent focus on the local level through the CCLLs while identifying opportunities for knowledge transfer at the European level through events, web channels (website, social media, newsletter) and contacts with other similar EU projects and initiatives.

2.4.10.4. Other non-scientific publications

Through various collaboration activities, SCORE was also featured in a number of external publications, among which we highlight the following:

- SCORE is featured in the [CORDIS’ projects info pack entitled “EU missions to address climate change in cities and regions”](#) published in June 2024 (see pages 22-23) alongside other EU projects supporting the work of the EU Mission Adaptation to Climate Change.
- SCORE was featured in the [“Sea’ties Regional Report – Adapting Coastal Cities and Territories to Sea Level Rise in the Mediterranean Region, Challenges and Best Practices”](#) where the SCORE project and its Coastal Cities Living Labs (CCLLs) are one of two case studies presented (see page 26-27). This report was published with the support of the City of Marseille, Plan Bleu and MedECC and was presented on 12 November 2022 during the COP27, both online and at the Mediterranean Pavilion.
- Following the project’s contributions to the COP27, SCORE was highlighted as a **featured project** by CINEA: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/featured-projects/score-coastal-city-living-lab_en.

2.4.10.5. Scientific publications

The consortium is actively disseminating its results through several scientific publications. The KPIs set at the beginning of the project have already been reached: **30 scientific publications** in Scopus Indexed peer-reviewed journals, **one special issue/ collection** in a peer-reviewed journal, and **10 conference proceedings**.

At M36, **59 scientific publications have been already published (36 journal articles, 6 conference abstracts, 12 conference papers, 3 editorials, 1 book chapter, and 1 special issue)**. All these publications have been uploaded in the SCORE Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project>.

SCORE partners are committed to publish in high-ranking journals, especially in the last six months of the project (January-June 2025), to effectively disseminate their key findings and enhance the impact of the project. At this scope, below is the list of well-established and influential journals in the field that partners have selected, with an indication of the results to be disseminated and related WP.

Table 4: List of targeted journals in 2025

Journal	Impact Factor	Topic of the article / result to be disseminated
Journal of Cleaner Production	9,8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Living labs contextualization, monitoring, and evaluation (WP2)
Science of the Total Environment	8,2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate-Induced Flood Modeling and Water Cycle Dynamics in the Kızılırmak Delta, Turkey (WP3) Multi-hazard risk assessment methodology (WP7) Enhancing coastal cities' resilience to flood and storm surge through Digital Twins: three case studies (WP8)
Environmental Science & Policy	4,9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low-cost sensors (WP4)
IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine	16,2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Review of Technical Challenges in Opportunistic Rainfall Estimation Using Satellite and Terrestrial Microwave Links (WP5)
Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences	4,2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative flood risk assessment for European coastal cities (WP6)
Journal of Environmental Management	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic valuation of costs and benefits of EbA measures in the frontrunner CCLLs (WP7)
IEEE Internet of Things Journal	9,47	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SCORE DT-EWS architecture and functionalities and validation (WP8)

2.4.11. Events

The SCORE project partners are organising and participating in several events for dissemination and knowledge transfer purposes, as detailed below.

2.4.11.1. Organisation of events

Below is the list of the events that is planned to be organised by the end of the project:

- Local community events: 3 **EBAs training schools** in the 10 CCLLs, **workshops** contextualizing the CCLL approach for each city, **citizen science workshops, hackathons**;
- 2 **international workshops** related to the project results;

- **Several webinars** to disseminate the project results to a wide range of stakeholders (one for each work package and every 2 months on average)
- A **final info day** to be organised at the end of the project

At M36, 1 international workshop, 2 EBA Training Schools, 10 webinars and several citizen science activities and workshops (e.g. Minecraft, smart pebbles) have already been organised.

Among these activities, we highlight:

- The organisation of the **first EBA Training School** (Year 2) in June-July 2023 (<https://score-eu-project.eu/2023/05/11/score-climate-adaptation-training-school-first-edition/>);
- The organisation of the **second EBA Training School** (Year 3) in March-April 2024 (<https://score-eu-project.eu/2024/02/09/score-climate-adaptation-training-school-second-edition/>);
- The organisation of the **first SCORE international workshop** organised at [the Open Living Lab Days on 22 September 2023 \(score-eu-project.eu\)](https://score-eu-project.eu/2023/07/10/score-workshop-at-the-open-living-lab-days/) (<https://score-eu-project.eu/2023/07/10/score-workshop-at-the-open-living-lab-days/>);
- A series of 10 **webinars** organised by Euronovia from March 2022 to May 2024 to illustrate the work carried on within each work package and to boost dissemination of these activities and results as much as possible.

Further details on the events organised in the period M1-M24 are available in the mid-term report (D9.2) while a more detailed description of events organised until M36 will be included in the technical report of RP2 as well as in the Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities (D9.3).

Below is the list of events that are planned to be organised by SCORE in the final year of the project:

- A **workshop** entitled “Smart Technologies and Community Engagement with EBA for Climate Resilience Actions”, to be organised by ATU on September 24, 2024 at the Littoral24 conference in Constanta (Romania). In addition, we will also have a project booth for SCORE promotion and dissemination of results;
- **The 2nd SCORE international workshop** on “Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures” will be organised as a partner event of the EU Week of Regions and Cities (October 10, 2024 – Brussels, Belgium). This high-level event will be a valuable opportunity to showcase the project’s achievement to regional and local authorities from all over the EU. We will also be present at the conference with a project booth;
- **The third and final EBA training school** will be organised in the Spring 2025. It will showcase the tangible impact of the SCORE in each CCLL. Presentations, case studies, field visits, etc. will demonstrate the implemented solutions and their positive outcomes. CCLLs will also share their experience, challenges and best practices in implementing climate adaptation strategies.
- A **webinar** will be organised in the Spring 2025 as follow-up to the first CCLL framework webinar in order to present the results and achievements of this framework developed by the project. The organisation of other new **webinars** are also being discussed by the **Adapt4Coast cluster** (see section 2.4.11)
- The **SCORE final infoday** will be organised between M45 and M48 to present all the results and achievements of the project. In order to ensure wide participation in this event, several options are being considered: an event in Brussels to reach the EU community, a side event to a big conference related to coastal areas and climate adaptation, or in one of the CCLL to allow for site visits. At the time of writing this report, our first

choice will be to organise it as a side event to the European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) conference which will take place in Rimini, Italy, in June 2025. The format of this event will be a combination of presentations, and panel discussion, as well as an exhibition area where participants will be able to see and where possible utilise with SCORE's various tools.

2.4.11.2. Participation in events

Members of the SCORE consortium regularly participate in different national and international events to raise awareness of the project, engage with specialist groups of stakeholders and disseminate the project results. For the whole project duration, the plan is to attend a range of different events to reach different audiences:

- 10 Scientific conferences** to promote the scientific and technical results of the project
- Organise 3 Exhibition fairs in technology and Open innovation related events;**
- At least 1 Science popularisation events** targeting the general public, and in particular students, citizens, local communities
- Participation in **local community events** (EBAs safari, citizen science, hackathons, etc.), **educational activities** (Summer schools and STEM activities in primary and secondary schools), **open innovation conferences**

List of targeted events for the next 6 months

Below (Table 5) is a list of the most relevant events and conferences that have been identified by project partners as strategic venues for dissemination of project results in the last six months of the project (January-June 2025). It is to be noted that, for some of these events, participation is subject to the submission of a formal application (session proposal or call for papers) and a selection by the organisers.

Table 5: List of relevant events to target by SCORE partners

Name	Date	Venue	Partner planning to attend
Precipitation Processes - Estimation and Prediction (PrePEP) conference	16–21 March 2025	Bonn, Germany	UNIFI
EGU25	27 April - 2 May 2025	Vienna, Austria	IHS, ENT, UCD
EU Maritime Days	21-23 May, 2025	Cork, Ireland	ATU, ERINN
European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA 2025)	16-18 June, 2025	Rimini, Italy	IHS, UCD, ENT, ATU, EUR, ERINN
European Urban Resilience Forum	25-27 June, 2025	Rotterdam, The Netherlands	IHS
19th International Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management (CUPUM)	23–27 June 2025	London, UK	UCD
ICUC12 – 12th International Conference on Urban Climate	7-11 July 2025	Rotterdam, The Netherlands	IHS

Attendance at strategic congresses and conferences

In each version of the SCORE PEDR (v1, v2, v3) we have provided a list of targeted events that partners identified as important venues for dissemination of project results. This list was originally quite extensive, and it was not intended that partners would participate in all the events. Therefore, not all the targeted events were ultimately attended, for several reasons: in some cases, participation was upon selection by the organisers (session or paper), in other cases

timing was not ideal to disseminate a certain result, or partners turned out to be already busy with other activities, or had to reconsider their participation due to budget or other internal constraints. Internally, we monitor attendance at these target events using an online living document that partners continuously update with information on their participation and with new relevant events identified (see overview of this tracking document in Annex 5).

This strategy has been updated for the last reporting period (RP3), based on reviewers' feedback: instead of including a long list of conferences in the field, that we are not sure partners will be able to attend, it was decided to highlight only a limited number of strategic events, where most efforts would be put towards, and where an application (session or abstract) has been already submitted by SCORE partners to the organisers.

A total of 59 target events (conferences and technology & innovation events) were listed in the different versions of the SCORE PEDR (v1, v2, and v3) and in the internal tracking document. By the end of RP2 (June 2024), the partners attended 27 of these events, representing 46% of the number of identified events in this time period.

In addition, 25 additional events (i.e. not listed in the documents mentioned above) were also attended by the SCORE partners, including some important events upon invitation only, some technical events or other events that partners hadn't initially included in the list. In conclusion, a total of 52 events were attended by 30 June 2024. More details can be provided by EUR to the EC upon request.

The list of attended events up to June 2024 can be found in the technical reports of RP1 and RP2. The final list will be included in the Final report on dissemination, communication and exploitation (D9.3).

2.4.12. Synergies with other projects & initiatives

In order to boost dissemination of project results and maximize impact, synergies are being developed with other **EU projects and initiatives working on a similar topic/domain**.

A list of projects with which SCORE could have synergies was drafted early after the launch of SCORE, taking into consideration a similar scope, activities and topic (climate change / coastal areas). This list was regularly updated and progressively refined, to include only those projects with which effective synergies were developed. **This list is available in Annex 4.**

Among these projects, we highlight our collaboration with the [CoCliCo](#), [PROTECT](#) and [REST-COAST projects](#) (see Table 5), with which synergies were stronger, since together we decided to apply for the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) and to join forces to constitute a **project group called Adapt4Coast** aiming to improve coastal city climate resilience.

Table 6: European projects participating with SCORE in the Adapt4Coast Cluster

Project acronym	Project objective	Website
CoCliCo 2021-2025	Informing decision-making on coastal risk and adaptation, by delivering an open web-platform exploring dominant risk drivers, adjusting visualisation and analysis techniques to local decision contexts, and combining relevant and high-quality geospatial information layers.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101003598/
REST-COAST 2021 - 2026	The project will bring together 38 partners to assess ecosystem services from coastal marshes, seabed meadows and coastal dunes, to reduce erosion and flooding risks while enhancing biodiversity and blue carbon. REST-COAST will conduct nine pilots in the main EU regional seas (Baltic, Black, North, Atlantic and Mediterranean) with the aim of increasing the commitment of citizens, stakeholders and policymakers.	https://rest-coast.eu/

PROTECT 2020 - 2024	<p>The project aims at leveraging innovation procurement to unlock the climate service market's potential. The initial focus will be on utilities, green cities, health, land use, marine environment and security. Eventually, PROTECT will provide decision makers at EU, national, regional and local levels, with practical recommendations and guidelines for climate action.</p>	https://www.protect-pcp.eu/
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As a cluster, we jointly developed a project video and factsheet, as well as a policy brief (<https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Adapt4Coast-Policy-Brief-Final.pdf>) including critical findings and valuable insights for government climate policy. We also organised a joint webinar on May 24, 2024, in which representatives of the four projects presented some of the tools and platforms under development to help communities plan smart adaptation strategies and play an active role in tackling climate-related challenges.

The cluster is being very successful in communicating and in disseminating the main outcomes of the projects involved, developing joint dissemination campaign on social media on different occasions. The impact of these activities is demonstrated by the attention received by the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, which invited the cluster to present the Adapt4Coast poster during the Third Forum for the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change in Brussels on May 23, 2024. The poster was presented by the SCORE coordinator on behalf of the cluster.

Collaborations with other EU projects and EU and international initiatives are regularly taking place.

These past months, different synergies have been set up, such as the SCORE participation in an **Ocean&Climate Platform** workshop on EbA in April 2024, a video-interview led by the **MAIA EU project** to the SCORE partners at ATU, meetings with another living lab in Ireland, a paper on the relationship between Digital Tools and NBS jointly drafted with the **EmpowerUs project**. SCORE is also an active participant in the **MIP4Adapt's Thematic Working Group** on Integrating Adaptation and Mitigation together with other projects, participating in three of its synergy workshops.

Some of the synergies with other projects planned in the final year include, but are not limited to: the organisation of joint webinars with the Adapt4Coast cluster, the participation in workshops and other events organised by other projects, cross promotion of project outcomes on websites and social media, the invitation of other project representatives to the SCORE final infoday.

2.4.13. Horizon Results Platform

As Key Exploitable Results (KER) are finalised, they are showcased on the EC's Horizon Results Platform to ensure maximal visibility. SCORE's [Co-create your City Toolkit](#) (KO 2.1) is available for view on the Horizon Results Platform. It contains a description of the result, relevant target audiences, the toolkit's unique value proposition and most notably, a seven-minute video which details the background to co-creation and how to use the toolkit. As SCORE's other KERs are finalised they will be showcased on the platform as well.

Figure 14: SCORE's Co-create your City Toolkit as presented on the Horizon Results Platform

2.5. Stakeholder engagement

The SCORE project employs a comprehensive approach to communication, dissemination, and knowledge transfer activities, catering to both the European/National level and the local/regional level within the Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs). This deliberate differentiation is a crucial element of the project's overall knowledge transfer and dissemination strategy since SCORE's outputs hold varying levels of significance at European, national, or local scales.

Recognising the diverse relevance of its outputs, the project acknowledges that certain outputs (i.e., flood maps) may have limited novelty on a European stage but can be highly valuable for CCLLs through a local/regional lens. On the other hand, some outputs may be groundbreaking at the European level but less intriguing for the broader academic audience. To address these differences, tailored dissemination strategies are implemented including through the knowledge management and transfer activities, ensuring the right stakeholders receive the appropriate information.

The purpose of this distinction is to optimise the support for the SCORE project by effectively sharing the appropriate results to the right stakeholders across different levels, at the right time. By recognising the fluidity of this process, the project understands that some outputs may be relevant and beneficial for both the European and local levels, and as such develops flexible and tailored dissemination strategies suitable for the identified actors and levels.

2.5.1. European/National level

To reach out the largest possible audience, each SCORE partners are using their own **networks of contacts** (see a non-exhaustive list in Table 6 below). Information on the project was sent out to some of these networks immediately after the launch of the project (July 2021) while others are being reached out for dissemination of project results or targeted communication to promote project events, webinars, and other activities (e.g. call for papers, etc.). This list is being updated regularly.

Table 7: Regional, national, European, and international networks used by the project partners.

ARegional and national networks	Country
Science Foundation Ireland Research Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine (MaREI) - https://www.marei.ie/	Ireland
OPW Office of Public Works - www.floodinfo.ie	Ireland
Climate Action Regional Offices or CARO - https://www.caro.ie/	Ireland
Legambiente Toscana (www.legambientetoscana.it)	Italy
WWF Toscana (www.wwf.it/chi-siamo/presenza-sul-territorio/toscana/)	Italy
CNR Firenze (http://www.area.fi.cnr.it/index.php/it/)	Italy
CNR Pisa (http://www.area.pi.cnr.it/)	Italy
Network of Sustainable Greek Islands (DAFNI) - https://dafninetwerk.gr/en	Greece
Cities Network DEPAN - https://depan.gr	Greece
CLIMATTICA®-Network of Greek Regions and Municipalities to fight climate change (new body - to be operational soon)	Greece
KEDE-Central Union of Municipalities of Greece - https://kede.gr/en	Greece
Hellenic Agency for Local Development and Local Government (E.E.T.A.A.) S.A - https://www.eetaa.gr/en_pages/index_en.php	Greece
iSea Environmental Organisation- https://isea.com.gr	Greece
Thermaikos gulf Protected Areas Management Authority - http://axiosdelta.gr	Greece
CERIS – Civil Engineering Research and Innovation for Sustainability (https://ceris.pt/)	Portugal
LNEC - Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (http://www.lnec.pt)	Portugal

NIB MBP – National Institute of Biology – Marine Biology Station, Environmental office of Municipality of Piran	Slovenia
Agencija Republike Slovenija za Okolje (ARSO) – Slovenian Environment Agency - https://www.arso.gov.si	Slovenia
Inštitut za vode Republike Slovenija (IzVRS) – Institute for Water of the Republic of Slovenia - http://www.izvrs.si	Slovenia
Geodetski inštitut Slovenije (GIS) – Geodetic Institute of Slovenia - https://gis.si/en/	Slovenia
lovensko društvo za morske sesalse (Morigenos) – Slovenian Marine Mammal Society	Slovenia
NATURKLIMA: Fundación de Cambio Climático de Gipuzkoa	Spain
Ingurumena - Hasieria (gipuzkoa.eus)	Spain
Xarxa de Ciutats i Pobles cap a la Sostenibilitat (Catalan Network of Cities and Towns towards Sustainability)	Spain
Ayuntamiento de Benidorm	Spain
INVATTUR, TURISME COMUNITAT VALENCIANA	Spain
DINAPSIS: Laboratorio de innovación ciclo del agua	Spain
DISTRITO DIGITAL CV	Spain
SEGITTUR	Spain
Xarxa per a la Conservació de la Natura / Nature Conservation Network (XCN)	Catalonia (Spain)
Carta Europea de Turisme Sostenible Parcs del Garraf, Olèrdola i Foix (CETS) - https://parcs.diba.cat/web/turisme-sostenible-als-espais-naturals/la-carta-i-el-parc/garrafolerdolafoix	Catalonia (Spain)
Taula de municipis per un litoral sostenible	Catalonia (Spain)
Consell Comarcal del Garraf - Comitè Tècnic Servei Medi Natural i Litoral - https://www.ccgarraf.cat/ambits/medi-ambient.htm	Catalonia (Spain)
Xarxa d'escoles per a la sostenibilitat de Catalunya (XESC) - http://escolesxesc.cat/ : Local Educational net is Agenda21Escolar - https://www.vilanova.cat/ciutat_verda/agenda_21_escolar	Catalonia (Spain)
European and international networks	
Open and Smart Agile Cities (OASC) - https://oascities.org/	
Eurocities - https://eurocities.eu/	
ALLIN (Australian Living Lab International Network) - https://www.australianlivinglabs.com.au/	
ISPIM community - https://www.ispim-innovation.com/	
Arup - https://www.arup.com/	
Climate Alliance - https://www.climatealliance.org/home.html	
Urban Climate Change Research Network	
EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy - https://www.covenantofmayors.eu	
European Sustainable Use Group - https://esug.sycl.net	
European Citizen Science Association - https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/	
Future Earth Coast - https://www.futureearthcoasts.org/	
Center for Applied Coastal Research - https://coastal.udel.edu/	
MARiNET - http://tierra.rediris.es/marinet/index.html	
Proplayas - http://www.proplayas.org/	
Atlantic Cities – http://atlanticcities.eu/en	
Ocean and Climate Platform: https://ocean-climate.org	
GD-SO Network of Multipliers - https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/environment-and-climate/european-green-deal/green-deal-projects-support/green-deal-resources	

2.5.2. Local / regional / CCLL level

In addition to the partner networks listed above, the CCLLs, within the context of the integrative living lab framework (WP2), have identified and regularly engage with a number of key local stakeholders and policymakers. Annex 2 provide a detailed list of the key stakeholders organised by category within the quadruple helix and locality.

Stakeholder engagement and knowledge transfer is an ongoing process for the CCLLs, and accordingly identified stakeholders have been either actively engaged with the CCLL, contacted by the CCLL or identified for future engagement/knowledge transfer.

Table 7 below shows the number of influential and prioritised stakeholders within each CCLL. *“Active” stakeholders* were defined as those that have both previously participated in prior activities (meetings, workshops, interviews, etc) and/or have committed to future activities/ collaborations. CCLLs listed a wide range of future workshops, meetings, interviews, citizen science activities, and academic collaborations with these active groups. These identified groups present an excellent opportunity moving forward for CCLLs for knowledge transfer as they already have an established relationship with the SCORE project. By virtue of being actively engaged in the CCLL, they were previously contacted by the CCLL core teams. *“Contacted” stakeholders* have been in communication with the CCLLs but have not yet participated in activities, while *“Other Identified Stakeholders”* are those stakeholders that have been identified as potential groups of interest for upcoming knowledge transfer. Both groups present opportunities to establish closer connections with the SCORE project. These groups will be engaged through the best practices previously observed with those identified as active stakeholders. These lists will continue to evolve over the course of the project.

Table 8: Level of engagement of priority stakeholders within each CCLL.

CCLL	Estimated Engagement Level of Stakeholder Group			
	Actively Engaged*	Contacted*	Other Identified Stakeholders*	Total
Benidorm	18	-	-	18
Dublin	12	9	5	26
Gdansk	18	12	2	32
Massa	44	4	-	48
Oarsoaldea	18	21	29	68
Oeiras	47	-	-	47
Piran	27	-	1	28
Samsun	14	9	-	23
Sligo	22	27	11	60
Vilanova	33	-	-	33
Total	253	82	48	383

* Actively engaged are those stakeholders that have or will soon participate in events/activities within the CCLL. * Contacted stakeholders have been reached out to by the CCLL and have received information, but not actively participated in events/provided inputs. ** other identified stakeholders are those who have not yet been engaged with but has been identified as a key knowledge transfer stakeholder group.

As detailed in Table 8 below, the CCLLs key stakeholders have been collected and categorised by type (Academic, Civil Society, Government, Industry) and level (Local, Regional, National). Knowledge transfer at a local level is a key

priority for SCORE and this is supported by the breakdown of the stakeholder groups, with over 50% of identified stakeholder groups were classified as local by the CCLLs.

Table 9: Organisational level for each category of active stakeholders across all CCLLs.

Engaged and Identified Stakeholders across the 10 CCLLs								
	Academic		Civil Society		Policy & Public Authorities		Industry	
	Engaged*	Identified**	Engaged	Identified	Engaged	Identified	Engaged	Identified
National	16	1	6	3	17	5	13	3
Regional	12	11	9	-	35	7	17	11
Local	17	2	79	-	50	3	43	2
Total	59		97		117		89	

* Engaged are those stakeholders that have been actively engaged and/or invited by the CCLLs to engage. ** Identified are those stakeholders who have not yet been engaged with, but has been identified as a key knowledge transfer stakeholder group.

2.5.3. Policy & Policymaker considerations

Engagement with local and regional policymakers is a high priority for the SCORE project amongst all knowledge transfer activities for the CCLLs. As indicated in Table 8 above, over 100 policymakers/government entities have been identified by the CCLLs, with over 80% of those being at the local or regional level. Policymakers are an essential stakeholder group for the progress of the project, and they are continually and routinely engaged, whether this is by invitation to the CCLLs various workshops, notably during the MCA/CBA (WP2/7) sensor (WP4) selection workshops, during other community outreach activities, amongst others. The current engagement with policymakers at the CCLL level is ongoing.

All CCLLs are keenly considering how to support relevant existing policies and contribute towards the policies goals, and where relevant, actively influencing and developing upcoming policies. Corresponding, the CCLLs have collated relevant policies (Annex 3) and identified, where relevant, the SCORE work packages/results that were best connected to these policies. The identification of the relevant work package to the policies serves as a key tool used during the KTP development process to provide more specific recommendations to the CCLLs. Table 9 provides an overview of the number of identified policies by policy level (National, Regional, Local). The engagement with the local and regional policymakers is not only necessary for achieving sufficient impact, but also this engagement is a key part of the CCLLs sustainability planning and future proofing. This list of policies will continue to be developed and evolve going forward in accordance with the identified project KOs and used to develop KTPs.

Some completed activities relevant to the dissemination and exploitation with policy-makers include:

- SCORE partners met the Mayor of Massa (Italy) and discussed about the project expected outcomes, on the occasion of the technical meeting organized in Massa in November 2021;
- In November 2022 the joint policy brief prepared with PROTECT & CoCliCo & SCORE were presented at the 27th United Nations Climate Change conference (COP27) in Sharm El Sheikh, Egypt by the CoCliCo project coordinator;

- Presentation of the SCORE project in the fifth edition of the “EU Policy event (F2P) 2023 for Climate Science projects”, organised by CINEA in cooperation with the DG Research and Innovation and DG Climate Action in March 2023;
- SCORE was presented at a workshop during the May Robinson Climate Conference (5-7 July 2023 - Ballina, Ireland) where many different city councils were present and could hear about the project;
- Knowledge Sharing Session during the Open Living Lab Days in September 2023.
- WP2 Fellows MCA/CBA Workshops took place in Fall 2023, whereby local policymakers/decisionmakers were invited to weigh in on future EBA utilisation/selection;
- Sligo presented their policy brief to the Sligo County Council in Fall 2023 and the project is now featured in the Climate Action Plan for Sligo: [sligococo.ie/Environment/ClimateAction/SCCClimateActionPlan2024-2029/SCC Final LACAP.pdf](https://sligococo.ie/Environment/ClimateAction/SCCClimateActionPlan2024-2029/SCC%20Final%20LACAP.pdf). Other CCLLs are using this as an example to support future engagements.
- The Oeiras CCLL team developed a policy brief during a local activity run through the EBA Training School Year 2. It focuses on understanding the increasing prevalence of heatwaves in Portugal. The team is using this to communicate studies on climate change impacts to local policymakers across Portugal and there are plans to disseminate this resource linked with knowledge outputs collected from Oeiras. The policy brief is available on the IST-ID website, as well as the SCORE website here: <https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/SCORE-Policy-Brief-Oeiras.pdf>.

Upcoming activities relevant to the dissemination and exploitation with policymakers include:

- The development of Policy briefs & recommendations within T7.5 (Policy recommendations to assist decision making in climate change adaptation at the local, national and EU level – M37-47) as part of D7.5. WP9 will support WP7 in the exploitation and dissemination of these guidelines.
- We are exploring the possibility of organising a session in which CCLLs will present their activities and relevant results relevant to policy makers and decision makers, either during the 3rd SCORE EbA Training School or as part of the final infoday.

Table 10: Organisational level for identified relevant policies by each CCLL.

CCLL	Policy Level			Total
	National	Regional	Local	
Benidorm	3	-	1	4
Dublin	2	-	1	3
Gdansk	-	2	-	2
Massa	2	2	-	4
Oarsoaldea	-	10	3	13
Oeiras	-	-	2	2
Piran	1	-	2	3
Samsun	2	3	2	7
Sligo	2	1	3	5
Vilanova	2	3	3	8
Total	14	21	17	52

2.6. Tracking and monitoring of the actions

The partner leading WP9 (Euronovia) is responsible for tracking all the communication and dissemination activities of the partners, to be used to evaluate their impact. At this scope, a document composed of 4 different spreadsheets was created in June 2021 to gather information related to the activities implemented by each partner, namely:

- Communication actions:** partners list and give details about all the communication activities done at the level of their organisation to promote the project;
- Scientific dissemination activities:** partners list and give details about their dissemination activities aiming to share the project's results;
- Scientific publications:** partners list all their publications (papers, conference proceedings, etc) in which SCORE research and results are used;
- Open research data:** partners list all the data sets gathered during the project duration.

Two additional tabs have been included later in the document in order to help the project partners share relevant information with the consortium:

- Events to target:** partners regularly list interesting events and conferences relevant for SCORE where participation could be envisaged;
- Networks:** partners keep track of the list of networks they are in contact with and that can be reached to disseminate project activities, events and results.

This document was uploaded to the project SharePoint platform in June 2021 and all partners are being reminded to update it as soon as they are involved in a communication or dissemination action to keep track of all the activities implemented within SCORE. An overview of this document is available in Annex 5.

2.7. Impact assessment

A detailed communication and dissemination plan was created at M6 in order to check that all activities are planned and are effectively taking place, integrating **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** to measure the impact of each dissemination and communication activity. KPIs are a measuring factor for the performance and progress of an activity, message, task, etc. towards its expected impact. Several KPIs have been defined for each communication activity. They are being used to assess the performance of the dissemination activities all along the project duration and re-orientate the dissemination plan when KPIs are not matched, and the expected impact not reached.

The project communication and dissemination plan including the detailed list of all communication and dissemination activities planned within the project, related KPIs and responsible partners, is available in the project SharePoint platform accessible only to members of the consortium and to the EC, upon request.

Using inputs from partners to the document tracking communication and dissemination actions, we elaborated a dissemination impact analysis to evaluate the impact of these actions, to know the type and number of people reached and to check if KPIs planned have been met. Euronovia regularly monitors these KPIs and take corrective measures if necessary (as described in the different sections of this report).

The in-depth analysis of KPIs up to M24 is available in the Mid-term report on communication and dissemination (D9.2) submitted in June 2023, while the table presenting the KPIs reached at M36, compared to targets that have been set to measure the success of the communication and dissemination actions at the end of the project (M48) is

available in Annex 6. For this evaluation at M36, the targets were adapted to proportionally fit the expected targets due at M36 (e.g., if 10 publications are expected by M48, we consider that the target at M36 is 8 publications).

The following scale was used to score each KPI:

- If the results are lower than 50% of the target, the result is considered as Low
- If the results are lower or equal to 75% but above 50%, the result is considered as Moderate
- If the results are lower or equal to 100% but above 75%, the result is considered as Good
- If the results are higher than 100%, the result is considered as High

The analysis shows that, at M36, we are well on track with our KPIs: as summarised in the table below, over 60% of our KPIs have received a “High” score, and over 80% have received either a “High” or “Good” score.

Table 11: KPIs' performance at M36

Score	High	Good	Moderate	Low
% of KPI	63%	19%	13%	6%

Most of the lower-performing KPIs are related to social media which can be explained as the KPIs set for these activities were very high from the start (target: +3000 followers on LinkedIn, +2000 followers on Twitter, +500 on Facebook and Instagram).

The final impact assessment analysis will be included in the D9.3 which will be submitted at the end of the project (M48).

3.KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND TRANSFER METHODOLOGY

3.1. Knowledge management and transfer overview

To ensure SCORE maximises its impact by exploiting results the project employs a proven Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology. This methodology was originally developed in the FP7 MarineTT project (GA #244164), and further developed and applied by the H2020 COLUMBUS project (GA #652690 - www.columbusproject.eu). This methodology has been applied in many FP7 and Horizon 2020 funded projects such as AQUAEXCEL, AQUAEXCEL2020, AquaInnova, ARRANA, COEXIST, COMMON SENSE, ECsafeSEAFOOD, MaCuMBA, MG4U, ParaFishControl, MATES, SIMBA, ERGO REvived water, RES4BUILD, SEALIVE, BIOGEARS, SEArcularMINE, TechOceanS and ESCAPE.

SCORE's Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology is designed in a way to compliment the aforementioned dissemination and communication activities and overarchingly, to ensure the continued targeted impact of all knowledge transfer activities and foster exploitation of SCORE's results.

All captured knowledge will be assessed and recorded in line with the Consortium Agreement (CA), respecting privacy and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) requirements. This approach is essential to avoid unforeseen delays or obstacles related to confidentiality or competitiveness and to provide partners with the security they need to allow them to be transparent in their findings, enabling the project to quickly identify opportunities for exploitation. The objective is to ensure the fastest route for new knowledge to where it can add value and create impact.

Table 12: List of relevant definitions for knowledge management and transfer

Definitions
<p>Knowledge Management is the process of identifying, capturing, organising, analysing, and storing knowledge (project results and outputs) to ensure its availability to be transferred effectively to specific and relevant users.</p>
<p>Knowledge Transfer (KT) is the overall process of moving knowledge from knowledge sources to targeted potential users, focusing the research being conducted on the wider needs of society and industry. KT consists of a range of activities that aims to capture, transmit and exploit knowledge, skills, and competencies from those who generate them to those who will transform them into added value outcomes, thus maximizing impact. It can include commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, licensing, spin-off creation, researcher mobility, and publications. The ultimate end benefit of successful KT is the application and influence of knowledge on targeted groups with greater impact (short and long-term) across academia, industry, and society.</p> <p>This methodology focuses on capturing all the project's 'Knowledge Outputs' (KOs) and, through a series of collections and prioritisation, identifying the 'Key Exploitable Results' (KERs).</p>
<p>Knowledge Outputs (KOs) are described as "a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a scientific project. It is not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge". Typically, such knowledge might be referenced as a small part of a published paper, potentially three to five years after the approach is pioneered in a research project.</p>

Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are the ‘tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature’ which have been deemed to be of high priority for project transfer actions. How KERs will be identified from KOs is described in Section 3 of the PEDR, but it is important to note that SCORE is not implying any sort of value judgement between KOs and KERs. Rather, the project is simply using this distinction to allow knowledge that is of the most direct impact to the project or is most feasibly transferrable by the project, to be prioritised when assigning resources for transfer. By focusing on identifying KERs and transferring them when they have been assessed as having potential application and impact, it is possible to fast track them, providing a faster impact on target- and end-users external to the project.

End-user(s) are the individual(s) who are identified as being in a position where they could feasibly apply a given unit of Knowledge (KO/KER) and by so doing create the desired eventual impact of that knowledge. The KO/KER may need to evolve in order to reach the end-user.

Target User is an individual(s) whose position makes them a potential stepping-stone needed along the impact pathway for a KO/KER to progress towards an identified end-user and eventual impact. Target users are individuals with a specific mandate or responsibilities relevant to the specific KO/KER being evaluated. Target users should not merely be potential users of knowledge but should be individuals whose application of the knowledge is likely to advance it down the relevant Knowledge Transfer Pathway. There can be any number of target users in a Knowledge Transfer Pathway.

A **Knowledge Transfer Plan** (KTP) is an analysed stepwise plan for achieving the identified eventual impact of any piece of knowledge, regardless of whether this impact is achievable in the short, medium, or long term. In SCORE these will be applied to all assessed KERs. The KTP identifies the end-user capable of producing the desired eventual impact and outlines a specific series of transfer activities to intermediate target users that provide a feasible plan to reach them.

Eventual Impact is the ultimate end benefit of the application of the knowledge (KO/KER). It is defined as an overall enhanced situation, generally for society but it can also be research or industry specific. Eventual impacts can be the adoption of new technologies, products or innovation identified and refined within the project or a change in protocols.

3.2. Knowledge management and transfer for SCORE

The Knowledge Management Strategy (KMS) and Knowledge Transfer of KO/KERs is integrated into the project through WP9, specifically in T9.3. The KMS is based on regularly collecting project KOs through structured questionnaires and interviews with partners responsible for developing the results. Collected and analysed KOs will be assessed by the Innovation Manager (MBI) and Innovation Board based on several criteria, including their innovation capacity, relevance to the respective sector, adherence to the project and call objectives, relevance at the local/regional levels for the CCLs, and overall expected impact. The Innovation Board also discusses the most suitable exploitation and targeted dissemination activities, as well as the most relevant target and end users to prioritise. The Innovation Board consist of all project SMEs (MBI, RED SpA, EUR, ENT, TERO, and ERINN).

ERINN (T9.3 leader) monitors knowledge generated by carrying out regular collection rounds (M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48, M54). These collections are iterative, involving questionnaires, interviews and rounds of reviews to ensure all information is clear and up-to-date. All Knowledge Outputs (KOs) collected are analysed with support from the IB and relevant partners, to identify the project’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and assess whether IP protection

is necessary. For the identified KERs, ERINN develops Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs), detailing customised transfer activities for the target and end-user(s).

KTPs are submitted to the Innovation Board and relevant partners for review and input, ensuring SCORE innovations are in line with the latest market needs and expectations and/or ensuring the KTPs are tailored to the CCLL's local contexts. The Innovation Board and KTPs consider the potential routes to maximize impact of the KO/KER for at both the European/national level and regional/local CCLL level. As such, the KOs/KERs are reviewed for both their relevancy, novelty, use and exploitation potential at a European level and the CCLL/local level.

ERINN and Euronovia will support the KO/KER owners and CCLL core teams, in planning the implementation of KTPs (identifying relevant stakeholders, events etc.) and dissemination/exploitation activities needed for transfer. SCORE's KT methodology will develop transfer plans that are tailored to the respective target user. This customised approach will increase the likelihood that 1) KOs/KERs will be transferred and exploited successfully, and the result will be applied; 2) there is an increased potential for impact from the transfer; 3) it is possible to measure and demonstrate the impact of the transfer.

To support the successful engagement of SCORE partners with this methodology, an internal special workshop organised to deal with exploitation and the protection of results took place during the Sligo Consortium Meeting (June 2022) to showcase the methodology and provide a practical overview of the knowledge management methodology. Subsequently, collected KOs/KERs and practical reminders about the KTP methodology were presented at the Alicante Consortium meeting (2023) and the Gdansk Consortium meeting (2024). The consortium will continue to be kept informed of all knowledge transfer activities and KOs in the final year of the project to support overall project impact and to ensure protection of results with potential commercial applications. Finally, these KOs/KERs will be presented to the consortium (webinar/one-day seminar) at the end of the project, outlining the actions required to fulfil their market potential. The partners have access to the KOs on SCORE's SharePoint and can review them at any point. All partners should be aware of [IP policy and the Code of Practice](#) concerning the management of IP as stated by the recommendation from the EC.

3.2.1. Cross Cutting Principles

SCORE is a highly integrated and complex project, and therefore the knowledge management process requires a corresponding robustness. The project has been designed in such a way to ensure that knowledge management and knowledge transfer are cross-cutting activities across the project. Notably, ERINN as Task 9.3 leader, is involved in knowledge transfer and impact related tasks across three technical work packages and across WP9. Details are outlined below.

- Within **WP2** (Coastal City Living Labs Design, Implementation, and Evaluation), ERINN leads Task 2.8 – “Knowledge Production & Exchange” (M6 – M48) and is actively engaged across the WP2 tasks, including the workshops involving local stakeholders. Within Task 2.8, ERINN regularly holds “lessons learned” (LL) meetings with the CCLLs and technical partners to assess and reflect on the implementation of the living lab methodology and associated technologies. This will ultimately lead to the development of D2.4 (Final CCLL Knowledge Products and Lessons Learned). However, these interactions and engagement across WP2 supports the KT activities by allowing ERINN to better understand the CCLL priorities and their respective local contexts, engage with the CCLLs during the implementation of the Pilot Operational Plans, including providing guidance on the local dissemination activities. ERINN works closely with Naider on Task 2.6 Learning exchanges (LE) between frontrunner and follower CCLLs to ensure that not only are the results and experiences of the CCLLs disseminated and opportunities for exploitation are shared amongst the CCLLs, but that the best-practice principles and activities are documented extensively, to

support the development of future CCLLs beyond SCORE's 10 CCLLs. Lastly, WP9 is utilising the CCLL's stakeholder identification and prioritisation, climate action plan development and ENOLL's CCLL mentorship activities to support KT activities, to ensure sufficient impact and the long-term sustainability of the CCLLs contribute to the success.

- Within **WP6** (Strategies to increase the financial resilience of coastal cities), ERINN partners on Task 6.5: Decision-support guidelines for policymakers (M30-44), to ensure that ERINN is active in the development of such guidelines, and therefore can support the CCLLs (who partner on this task) in the effective implementation of these guidelines, identifying relevant policymakers and policies to target, and develop associated KTPs at a CCLL level.
- Within **WP7**, WP9 will support WP7 partners in the implementation of Task 7.5, which focuses on formulating policy recommendations to aid decision-making in climate change adaptation at local, national, and EU levels. This task aims to gather evidence on coastal ecosystem services and adaptation costs and benefits, sharing success stories to demonstrate public value from adaptation measures. WP9 will assist in the potential design of these policy recommendations and will support the dissemination of the outcomes to ensure effective policy uptake and implementation through the established KT methodology. To date, WP7 and WP9 have liaised in regard to this task and are in alignment on a timeline of this work.
- Within **WP8** (Development of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin solution prototypes), ERINN partners on Task 8.4 (Integration and Deployment of GIS based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform: M24-48) and Task 8.5 (Assessment of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin: M24-48). Notably, the KT methodology has been incorporated into the Impact Assessment for the digital twin (DT) and early warning system (EWS) implementation. The impact assessments will include the development of KTPs for each CCLL as related to the DT and EWS.
- ERINN has an active role supporting WP leader Euronovia in **WP9** (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation), specifically, ERINN is a key member of the EBA Training School Team and leads the development of the MOOC (Task 9.6 – EBA Training Schools: M6-48) to facilitate exploitation via the [SCORE MOOC platform](#) on a large European level and within the CCLL communities.

Additionally, while ERINN does not have time in WP7, close collaborations between WP9 and WP7 have already been planned and discussed. Within WP7, WP9 will support WP7 partners in the implementation of Task 7.5, which focuses on formulating policy recommendations to aid decision-making in climate change adaptation at local, national, and EU levels. This task aims to gather evidence on coastal ecosystem services and adaptation costs and benefits, sharing success stories to demonstrate public value from adaptation measures. WP9 will assist in the potential design of these policy recommendations and will support the dissemination of the outcomes to ensure effective policy uptake and implementation through the established KT methodology. To date, WP7 and WP9 have liaised in regard to this task and are in alignment on a timeline of this work.

For the final year of the project, many of these cross-cutting activities have been planned in order to maximise use of the CCLL's time and to logically collect necessary information for all work packages. Table 12 below details the proposed timeline for KO collection and learning exchanges from M36- the end of the project. This is a proposed timeline and can be adjusted to CCLL capacity.

As a note, KO collection is ubiquitous across all work packages, but the KOs included in this timeline are collection plans that have been discussed at the Gdansk consortium meeting and prioritised over the next several months. Additional KOs will be identified and collected according to KO collection rounds that will take place periodically

throughout the project, and they will be reflected in this plan. Overall, KT activities will take place throughout the project and all results will be highlighted, even if they are not currently indicated in the below work plan.

Table 13: Cross-Cutting Principles Plan for the final phase of the project

Key Abbreviations: Lessons Learned (LL), Learning Exchange (LE)

WP	July - September	October - December	January - March	April- end of Project
WP1	KTP1.2 review, discuss CCLL case studies	LL Collection: WP1 with CCLLs KT Activities: 1) International Conference on Coastal Engineering 2) European Geosciences Union; General Assembly		
WP2	KTP2.1 Review, KTP2.2 Review LE: Sustainability sessions - linked to LL	LE: Sustainability sessions - linked to LL	LL Collection: Meetings with CCLLs and with WP leads LE: sustainability plans & evaluation exchange results with all partners	LE: Overall project lessons
WP3	KO Collection: Models for coastal hazard predictions	LE: WP3 to Frontrunners		
WP4	KTP4.1 review: Considering options for citizen science platforms CCLL Board Meeting: Discuss data management of the sensors and legacy			Citizen Science Playbook Finalised
WP5	LE: GeoStory development, CCLL profiles, and dissemination tips	Innovation Board Review: KO5.1		
WP6	KTP6.2 review KO Collection: Financial resilience software tool KO Collection: Decision support tool	Internal KT: WP6 to Frontrunners (Oarsoaldea, Vilanova, Massa) KO Collection: Policy guidelines LE: WP3 and WP6 Frontrunners to Fellows		
WP7	KTP7.1 review KTP7.2 review	Collect KO: EBA Implementation LE: MCA Experiences Frontrunners to fellows	LE: Policy briefs and dissemination experiences from CCLLs LE: CBA results and real usability - experience from frontrunners to fellows	KT of WP7 Policy outputs
WP8	Frontrunner KTP: Massa	Frontrunner KTP: Oarsoaldea Frontrunner KTP: Vilanova		LE: WP8 Digital Twin Frontrunners to fellows

WP9	Open KO Collection Round Develop MOOC - EBA Training School Year 2	Innovation Board Meeting	Innovation Board Meeting	Final KO Collection
	LITTORAL conference (include promotion of Sea'ties Policy Brief)	EU Week of Cities and Regions	EBA Training School Year 3	MOOC (EBA Training School Year 3)
		Open KO Collection Round	Finalisation of existing KOs	Innovation Board Meeting Final Info Day, Finalisation of if WP9 materials: brochure, press kits, KTPs

3.2.2. KT Training and Support Activities

The methodology of engaging the CCLLS in KT is a central part of WP9 and is consciously incorporated into the knowledge transfer methodology. In addition to the KT methodology, a number of supporting KT activities have been taking place to further engage the CCLLS.

At the CCLL/local level, ERINN has facilitated communication and dissemination strategy session with the WP2 Frontrunners, helping them to facilitate their KT strategies within their CCLL. These sessions took place for the WP2 Fellows in the Fall 2023. Overall, due to the presence of ERINN in WP2, the KT perspective is present throughout CCLL activities, including learning exchanges and lessons learned collections. Further dissemination trainings and KT knowledge sharing sessions have been facilitated at the CCLL Board Meetings and during the Year 1 & 2 Consortium, as well as a developing and distributing Communication & Dissemination Guidelines and corresponding Knowledge Transfer Strategy Template (Annex 1) for the CCLLS to utilise. Alongside these activities, ERINN has developed infographics with the CCLLS and WP2/7 partners (see 2.5.5), in their relevant local languages, to share the results of the MCA process with local stakeholders.

3.2.3. Knowledge Transfer Impact Assessment

Within the KTPs, KERs are assigned a current **Impact Readiness Level (IRL)**, and a target IRL to be achieved near or just beyond the end of the SCORE project as a measure of impact quantification. IRLs were first conceived by the EU-funded DANDELION Project in 2018 (GA: 693796) and have been adapted here to incorporate elements of the impact pathway model arising from the EU-funded RI-PATHS project. The Impact Readiness Level (Annex 6) provides an assessment of how 'actionable' knowledge is in the societal and policy context. Proxy indicators are used to reflect various types of stakeholder engagement along the impact pathway that are conducive to impact generation. These indicators acknowledge that pathways are not always linear, recognising that in many cases systemic and/or sustained engagement can be required to achieve a desired impact. The IRLs have also been mapped to the more widely recognised Technology Readiness Levels and Societal Readiness Levels for comparison.

IRL's have been selected as the mechanism to track the KER's impact and the holistic advancement of SCORE's knowledge. As such, SCORE's KTPs do not have a traditional quantification measure (i.e., reach x number of stakeholders or x number of downloads) as these actions, while fulfilling dissemination/exploitation criterion does not necessarily measure impact holistically, but rather measures the progress of one or two specific knowledge transfer activities. Certain knowledge transfer activities will be more impactful than others (i.e., having one-to-one meetings with a single local policymaker vs emailing a policy brief to 10 policymakers), despite the action equating to a lower KPI. Rather than selecting more traditionally quantifiable KPIs, which may assess the impact progression

more narrowly, the IRL measures progress more holistically and is therefore the selected impact measurement for SCORE.

The progression of the IRL will be supported by monitoring the knowledge transfer activities, accordingly each KTP includes a number of KT activities to track to provide the KO owners will guidance on what on what will support the progression of the KER up the IRL scale. The IRL levels will be monitored over the course of the project to ensure that the knowledge is moving along as anticipated/outlined in the KTPs.

3.3. Knowledge management & Transfer Steps and Protocols

This section of the PEDR outlines the stepwise process which will be carried out within T9.3. This methodology will see KOs identified, collected, reviewed, and prioritised to project KERs with developed KTPs. Figure 15 provides an overview of the full knowledge transfer pathway. The following sections will explain specific steps of this methodology and demonstrate how each step contributes to the overall knowledge transfer process.

The Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology consists of the following three overall phases and is further described in detail below:

- Collect and Understand**
- Validate and Analyse**
- Transfer and Exploit**

Figure 15: SCORE Full Knowledge Transfer Pathway and Methodology

3.3.1. Collect & Understand

Phase 1: Capturing of KOs in an internal KO Questionnaire (KOQ).

Effective KT relies on careful identification and description of KOs to ensure that all key information is provided which will result in effective transfer (Figure 16). This phase aims to understand the positioning of a KO to more efficiently carry out impactful KT activities. It intends to help clarify how the KO could be beneficial to different target and end-users. This step identifies potential applications, target and end-users and the eventual impact of a KO. The KOs will be collected in a Knowledge Output Questionnaire (KOQ – See Annex 7) and further clarified through engagement with the KO owner.

Within this phase, quality control measures will be performed to ensure that the KO(s) can be clearly understood by others, including those who may not be experts in the relevant disciplines. Each partner will treat information from other partners as confidential, unless otherwise stated, and not disclose it to other parties unless the information is publicly available. All beneficiaries need to note that KOs are not only the final results of research, but they can also be part of the methodology to obtain the final result, which could be an innovation for the whole research area.

It should be noted that KOs, especially those collected early in the project, are likely to continue to develop throughout SCORE. Collected knowledge will be periodically reviewed by ERINN and the relevant partners will be asked to provide updates if applicable. An overview of the KOs is available on SharePoint, partners can advise ERINN if a given KO/KER needs to be updated.

Figure 16: SCORE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Collect and Understand

PROTOCOL – Phase 1 Collect & Understand

1. ERINN sends the Knowledge Output Questionnaire (KOQ – Annex 7) to SCORE Task Leaders every 6 months beginning in M18, who are requested to complete it and update it as appropriate.
2. If the Task Leader thinks another partner is better suited to provide the requested information, then they should send it on to the relevant person(s) or let ERINN know who this person is.
3. For all identified KOs from the questionnaire, ERINN arranges interviews with the KO owner(s) to better understand the knowledge collected and brainstorm potential uses and users of the KO.
4. After the interview, the KO owner(s) receive an updated draft of the KO to check for accuracy following the discussion. KO owner(s) respond with any corrections or suggested additions/edits promptly. In particular, this review should focus on:
 - 4.1. If the title of the KO(s) is sufficiently informative
 - 4.2. If the description of the KO(s) is sufficiently comprehensive for a non-expert to adequately understand the nature of the KO and to determine its possible application
 - 4.3. If the potential end-users of the KO, as well as the potential application by each of these end-users, is reasonable/desirable and if there are any other potential end-users
 - 4.4. If the KO(s) is publicly available or is subject to IPR protection, which would affect transfer mechanisms and next steps
5. Once the KO owner is satisfied with the accuracy of their KOs they will be marked as “confirmed” in the Knowledge Output Template (KO).
6. KOs advance to the validation and analysis stage.

Table 14: Overview of SCORE’s Knowledge Output Collection

Jul-21	Aug-21	Sep-21	Oct-21	Nov-21	Dec-21	Jan-22	Feb-22	Mar-22	Apr-22	May-22	Jun-22
M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12

Jul-22	Aug-22	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	Feb-23	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24
M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	May-25	Jun-25
M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48

	Task 9.3
	Knowledge Output Collection

3.3.2. Analyse & Validate

Phase 2: The collected KOs are reviewed and assessed for potential application and impact.

Once the KO has been signed off by the owner and ERINN, the KOs go through an internal review process with the support of the Innovation Board, whereby a more thorough evaluation of the KO and its applicability and readiness for transfer will be investigated (Figure 17). Due diligence will be undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the KO and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge can be identified. Following, KOs will be prioritised and those with the potential to have an impact will go through to the next step. An essential step in the SCORE knowledge management and transfer methodology is the identification of KO applications, potential impact and respective end-users (e.g., applications could be in various areas and sectors not just the one in the research area of the project) for each KO which has been assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Important aspects are prioritisation of high potential KOs, profiling target and end-users to gain valuable insight to inform successful Knowledge Transfer Plans, and identification of whether knowledge transfer should occur at the EU/national level, CCLL level or both. The identification of whether transfer should be prioritised at the EU/National level and/or CCLL level is a key step in the knowledge transfer process. Further, for those KO/KERs that are identified as priority for CCLL level knowledge transfer, the CCLLs that are frontrunners for that KO's work package may be prioritised amongst the CCLLs for transfer activities due to an availability of results. For example, within WP6, Massa, Oarsoaldea and Vilanova are frontrunners, so any KOs developed within WP6 will focus on the transfer activities within those localities as relevant results may only be available for the frontrunners.

The prioritisation process which occurs is not a ranking of the KO's importance but rather a method to help SCORE identify where to focus transfer and exploitation efforts to ensure maximize impact. For those prioritised, the Innovation Board with support of relevant partners will identify potential target users whose application of the knowledge would be of benefit in transferring it towards its eventual impact.

Those KOs that are validated and deemed to be of priority for the project will be re-labelled as Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and progressed to the third phase. Any KO that is not made a KER will continue to be periodically reviewed and updated as necessary. Any remaining KOs at the end of the project will still be captured as evidence of impactful research for final reporting. The identification of target users in the analysis stage is critical to laying the groundwork for transfer and exploitation plans in the third phase. The exercises in this phase may also serve to identify potential stakeholder's worth connecting with, even in cases where the knowledge may not yet be ready for transfer.

Figure 17: Methodology: Analyse and Validate

PROTOCOL – Phase 2 Analyse & Validate

1. ERINN will organise KO and KER “expert analysis meetings” with the Innovation Board and when relevant, invited members of the consortium and advisory board following the completion of Phase 1.
 - a. The frequency and makeup of these meetings will be determined in collaboration with the Project Coordinator (ATU) and Innovation Manager (MBI), as well as based on the current status of knowledge collection and management in the project.
2. At the expert analysis meetings, the Innovation Board carries out a thorough examination and evaluation of the KOs (collected so far), their applicability and readiness for transfer, and assessment of whether IP protection is necessary. For each KO, the following will be considered:
 - a. If the KO requires an IP assessment
 - b. If the KO is best suited for EU/National level exploitation, CCLL level exploitation or both.
 - c. Identification of all likely target and end-users. We encourage partners to be as specific as possible when determining potential end-users, and consider the following conditions:
 - i. Understand the user’s mandate or responsibilities
 - ii. Consider their background knowledge, attitude and practice about the issue
 - iii. Understand their knowledge needs
 - iv. Understand what and who may influence their decisions
 - v. Be aware of their preferred sources of information and knowledge.
 - vi. Identification of associated application and impact potential
 - d. The Innovation Board will address the likelihood of transfer for each presented KO, by providing a ranking. The Innovation Board cumulative ranking (scale of 1 to 3, 3 = highest likelihood for transfer) indicates whether this KO has a high likelihood of transfer and determines whether or not it should be prioritised as a KER based on its current status.
 - i. The ranking will include an assessment of whether or not transfer is most appropriate at the European level or at the CCLL level. If it is at the CCLL level, specific CCLLs may be identified (i.e., those CCLLs that are frontrunners in the WP corresponding to this KO).
3. After each expert analysis meeting, ERINN will adjust the KO where necessary, this may include requesting clarification from the KO owners or progressing the knowledge (changing the KO to a KER).
 - a. If an IP assessment was deemed necessary by the Innovation Board during the expert analysis meetings, the generating partner will be asked to complete an IP Assessment which will be reviewed by the Innovation Manager and appropriate board member(s) who will guide as necessary until all relevant parties

believe sufficient IP protection rules have been applied before the further dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the KO.

4. Those KOs that progress to KER status will undergo the activities outlined in Phase 3. For those KO's that were not ranked with a high likelihood for transfer, this KO and associated results will be reassessed in subsequent KO collection periods and the KO owner will be requested to input further information assuming the result has progressed in the previous 6 months.

3.3.3. Transfer & Exploit

Phase 3: Carry out and report on Knowledge Transfer activities; whilst measuring the impact of both the activity and the application of the Knowledge by the User(s).

For each KER, Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTP) will be developed. Implementing an efficient KTP that is tailor-made to the needs and capacities of specific target and end-users (profiled in phase 2) will maximize the chance of successful transfer resulting in uptake and application. The key to success is achieved through fully understanding the target and end-user and developing the KTP around them. There are several steps included in the KTP, and there are different routes it can go down to reach its eventual impact. KTPs are the accumulation of numerous KT activities as represented in Figure 18.

Within the KTPs, KERs will be assigned a current Impact Readiness Levels (IRL) and a target IRL to be achieved near or just beyond the end of the SCORE project as a measure of impact quantification or KPI. The Impact Readiness Level Model below provides an assessment of how 'actionable' knowledge is in the societal and policy context. The IRLs (Annex 6) have also been mapped to the more widely recognised Technology Readiness Levels and Societal Readiness Levels for comparison. The KER's IRLs will be monitored throughout the project duration to assess overall impact.

The individual partner(s) and/or CCLL(s) within SCORE best positioned to conduct the transfer will be identified and ERINN will support these partners to implement the KTPs. In this phase the impact of SCORE's KERs will be measured at regular intervals using the assigned and target IRL. KERs will be showcased on the EC's Horizon Results Platform outlining the actions required to fulfil their market potential.

The work carried out in this phase will be essential for impact generation and supported by activities to ensure the accurate reporting of the knowledge transfer activities. Not every KTP will be able to be reasonably executed during the lifetime of the project, but by delivering clear plans, the knowledge management methodology will help to establish how exploitation actions within the project will feed into the overall impact of the project as a whole and help achieve the societal goals of SCORE.

Figure 18: SCORE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Transfer and Exploit

PROTOCOL – Phase 3 Knowledge Transfer Planning & Exploitation

ERINN, with the support of Euronovia and the Innovation Board, will work with all relevant partners and CCLLs to assist where possible to implement the KTPs into knowledge transfer activities to engage with the appropriate target and end-users.

For any knowledge that has been determined to be a KER:

1. ERINN will collaborate with the Innovation Manager and Innovation Board and the owner(s) of a KER to develop a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) for each KER. It will consider:
 - a. The impact potential identified in the validation and analysis step ensures that a concise and compelling narrative for the opportunity/business case is developed.
 - b. The technical level of the target user; the depth of information needed; and the style of the language most effective for communicating with them.
 - c. The background knowledge of the target user.
 - d. Any preconceived ideas that the target user may have relating to the area of interest.
 - e. Ways in which to relate the knowledge to examples with which the target user is familiar, or ones they can easily envisage.
 - f. The level of evidence or validation that the target user requires.
2. ERINN will be responsible for drafting the KTPs, the nature of these knowledge transfer activities will be highly dependent on the KER, the target user(s), the transferring partner, timelines, and resources available.
 - a. Once the KTPs have been drafted, they will be reviewed by the coordination team, IB, generating partner(s) and when relevant, specific CCLLs for feedback. Following any necessary iterations, the KTPs will be finalised.
3. The knowledge transfer activities themselves are then carried out within a range of externally focused tasks by the KER owner, WP9, and/or relevant CCLLs.
 - a. Any action points/knowledge transfer activities outline by the IB Board, KO owners and CCLLs will be monitored and actioned by ERINN and EUR at monthly WP9 meeting
 - b. Support will be provided to ensure the success of these knowledge transfer activities.

4. KNOWLEDGE OUTPUTS & TRANSFER PLANS

This section includes an overview of the prioritised KOs to date and the associated KTPs that have been developed for those high prioritised KERs. The KTPs are developed to have specific knowledge transfer activities outlined for each of the target groups per KO. The target users and end-users for the KO's are diverse in their needs and expectations and as such, personalised plans are developed for each KO target group. The KTPs are written in a concise and straightforward manner to ensure easy uptake by SCORE partners and beyond the project.

The KTPs that have been developed to date are based on the KO's submitted to the ERINN and the Innovation Board to date. At present, 15 KOs were submitted to ERINN across 3 separate collection rounds periodically conducted throughout the project, as summarised in Table 13. After the assessment of the first two rounds by the Innovation Board, 7 KOs were deemed to be KERs, and the associated KTPs were developed. Table 14 below gives an overview of all KOs collected to date, along with their anticipated knowledge transfer level and their current status. Depending on when these KOs were collected, they are at different stages within the KT process, and this is reflected in their status.

Table 15: Overview of KOs collected at M36

Overview of KOs collected to date				
KO #	Title	WP	Primary Owner	Status
KO1.1	Mapping of baseline exposure and risks of climate change impacts on Coastal Cities.	WP1	UCC	Reviewed
KO1.2	Multi-hazard risk assessment methodology for climate change impacts on European Cities	WP1	UCC	Reviewed- KER
KO2.1	Co-Creation Toolkit	WP2	IHS, ENOLL	Reviewed- KER
KO2.2	Pilot Operational Plan (POP): A strategic framework for the establishment of living labs.	WP2	Naider	Reviewed- KER
KO3.1	Samsun CCLL short-term hazard models	WP3	SAMU	Reviewed
KO3.2	Flood inundation areas obtained as a result of short-term hazard modelling (Samsun CCLL)	WP3	SAMU	Reviewed
KO3.3	Models for coastal hazard predictions and climate impact maps (Samsun CCLL)	WP3	SAMU	Collected
KO4.1	SCORE Catalogue of low-cost sensors viable for citizen science activities	WP4	UCD	Reviewed- KER

KO5.1	SCORE ICT Platform (SIP)	WP5	UniPi	Collected
KO5.2	SensorThings API & Data Harvester	WP5	UniPi, TERO	Collected
KO6.1	Exposure database for frontrunner CCLLs Vulnerability curves for frontrunner CCLLs	WP6	Red Risk	Reviewed
KO6.2	Risk characterisation methodology for the development of semi-quantitative, comparable indices.	WP6	Red Risk	Reviewed- KER
KO7.1	Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, databases, and studies addressing ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) and other adaptation strategies	WP7	ENT, IHS, ENoLL, TERO	Reviewed- KER
KO7.2	Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change	WP7	ENT, IHS, ENoLL, TERO	Reviewed- KER
KO7.3	EBA Catalogue	WP7	ENT, ZRS	Collected
KO8.1	Digital Twin	WP8	MBI	Collected

Over the next few months of the project, additional KOs have been identified as potential KOs that will be collected in subsequent knowledge collection rounds. Table 15 below details a few of these proposed / upcoming knowledge outputs recently prioritised for collection at the Gdansk June 2024 consortium meeting. This list is by no means exhaustive.

Table 16: KOs Identified for Collection

KOs Identified for Immediate Collection			
Title	Work Package	Main Contact	Anticipated Knowledge Transfer Level
Baseline Characterization and Projections Procedure	WP3	Lamma	European
Downscaling Tools and User Document	WP3	Lamma	European
Statistical Analysis Tools & User Document	WP3	Lamma	European
Financial resilience software	WP6	RED	European
Decision support tool	WP6	RED	European and Local level
Cost benefit analysis	WP7	ENT, ATU	European and Local Level

4.1. Knowledge Transfer Plans

Knowledge Transfer Plans have been prepared for all Key Exploitable Results, though a number of these have not yet been included for distribution as the KO is not finalised and/or for IP protection/publishing reasons. KTPs for each KER will be finalised upon completion and validation by WP9 and KER owners, and are reassessed periodically throughout the project for any opportunities for updates. Below are three KTPs to serve as examples of this process.

4.1.1. KO2.1: SCORE Co-create your City Toolkit

Dissemination level: Public | **European/National Level or CCLL level Transfer:** European/National level

KO Description	
Short Title	SCORE Co-create your City Toolkit
KO Description	<p>This collection of co-creation tools can assist anyone in facilitating a multi-stakeholder process (including any target group across the quadruple helix) or activity related primarily to urban development. The collection of tools is somewhat generic allowing it to be adapted for other settings beyond urban development.</p> <p>The toolkit is structured around four categories based on the target/outcome of the co-creation activity (i.e., needs assessment, visioning, etc.). These categories mirror SCORE's living lab methodology. Users can select the tool to be used among the different categories. There is a series of selection criteria which can support them to choose the most appropriate tool within each category, such as the number of persons to be involved, the time required for facilitation, or the materials needed for facilitation.</p>
Owner(s)	IHS & ENOLL
Readiness	<p>Ready for uptake – active on IHS webpage: https://www.ihs.nl/en/advisory-training-and-research/tools-and-toolkits/co-create-your-city-toolkit</p> <p>Available on the Horizon Results Platform.</p>
Patent or other IPR	N/A
Knowledge Transfer Activity A	
Target User: Public Sector Facilitators	
Target User identified as:	<p>Public sector – facilitators/practitioners. These persons might not be explicitly trained in co-creation, but could facilitate a local session with relevant users.</p> <p>Examples: Public authorities (i.e., municipal departments), people working in academia, researchers, civil society organisations, non-profit</p>

	formal organisations (i.e., NGOs), organised communities, interest groups.
<p>Awareness:</p> <p><i>Is the Target User aware of the KO already?</i></p>	Target users may not necessarily be aware of this KO, but aware of the idea of co-creation more broadly and looking to utilise these activities, but lack the tools to do so.
<p>Level of Understanding:</p> <p><i>What level of technical understanding does your Target User have of the surrounding topic?</i></p> <p><i>Does the KO need translation (from technical to layman's terms)?</i></p> <p><i>Do they require training to take up the KO?</i></p>	<p>Implementers of the Toolkit (facilitators): Anyone falling within the quadruple helix can be implementer/facilitator, with the exception of an individual citizen.</p> <p>The individual tools are written in a highly accessible way, and have different components, including methods, templates (digital and/or printable) or online), and/or suggest software. Many of the instructions suggest amendments/personalisation that the facilitators can utilise if the conditions do not fit their needs perfectly.</p>
<p>Role/Responsibility of Target Users:</p> <p><i>What is the relevant role/responsibility of the Target User?</i></p>	For those facilitating a multi-stakeholder process (including any target group across the quadruple helix) or activity related primarily to urban development.
<p>Other Influences:</p> <p><i>Who else could be influencing the Target User's decisions?</i></p> <p><i>Do they have the authority to apply your knowledge? If not, who does and how can you access this person?</i></p>	Public authorities often need buy in from the municipality or higher-ups and approval to run these types of co-creation sessions. These sessions are also run based on the priorities of the regional/community. With that said, co-creation activities are becoming more known and common place, therefore, adoption should be more manageable.
Knowledge Transfer Activities	
<p>Message for Stakeholder</p> <p><i>Reasons why the knowledge is innovative, beneficial and, addresses the Target Users needs</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-created solutions are more locally embedded and thereby more sustainable. • Facilitating co-creation requires structures /methodology, which is simply laid out in this KO. • The toolkit provides a useful structure to bring together the quadruple helix. • Selecting a relevant tool can be overwhelming due to the number of options and tools, this provides a well organised and consolidated overview of options.

<p>Channel/Activities</p> <p><i>i.e., Email, face-to-face, social media, active networks</i></p> <p><i>A more specific calendar of activities is available to the internal SCORE team.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active networks (i.e., ENoLLs network) • Use the CCLL's success as a case study. • Webinars & how-to video • Emailing specific practitioners • Showcase on the MOOC, alongside the co-creation modules • Social media, specifically LinkedIn
Knowledge Transfer Activity B	
Target User: Other EU Projects & associated academics	
<p>Target User identified as:</p>	<p>Other EU / National projects utilising co-creation methods. Can link closely with the other projects using the Horizon Results Booster.</p> <p>I.e.: EmpowerUs, WaterLANDS, CLEVER cities, REWAISE, GrowGreen, Nature4cities</p>
<p>Awareness:</p> <p><i>Is the Target User aware of the KO already?</i></p>	<p>Aware of the idea of co-creation, but not specifically aware of this toolkit.</p>
<p>Level of Understanding:</p> <p><i>What level of technical understanding does your Target User have of the surrounding topic?</i></p> <p><i>Does the KO need translation (from technical to layman's terms)?</i></p> <p><i>Do they require training to take up the KO?</i></p>	<p>The toolkit should be quite usable for other academics/EU projects looking to co-create in urban settings. Generally speaking, academics and other projects have experience with these methodologies, experience implementing stakeholder activities, or the ability to easily fill their knowledge gaps.</p>
<p>Role:</p> <p><i>What is the relevant role/responsibility of the Target User?</i></p>	<p>For those facilitating a multi-stakeholder process (including any target group across the quadruple helix) or activity related primarily to urban development within an EU project.</p>
<p>Other Influences: <i>Who else could be influencing the Target User's decisions? Do they have the authority to apply your knowledge? If not, who does and how can you access this person?</i></p>	<p>Largely co-creation will already be embedded into the project design, or the coordination team write it in a proposal stage; the availability of such a toolkit simply reduces the necessity of a project building their own toolkit. If anything, European funding bodies are encouraging co-creation practices, so this may increase uptake.</p>
Knowledge Transfer Activities	
<p>Message for Stakeholder:</p>	<p>Provides an easy to access, ready to utilise toolkit, reducing the need for other projects to develop their own from scratch.</p>

<p><i>Reasons why the knowledge is innovative, beneficial and, addresses the Target Users needs</i></p>	
<p>Channel/Activities <i>i.e., Email, face-to-face, social media, active networks</i> <i>A more specific calendar of activities is available to the internal SCORE team.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences • Horizon Results Platform • Newsletter (SCORE and relevant partner newsletters, i.e., ENoLL) • Emails (partner/sister projects, advisory board, etc.) • Social media • Promoting internally to SCORE partners
Knowledge Transfer Evaluation	
<p>Knowledge Transfer Activity: How do you plan to evaluate this Knowledge Transfer Activity?</p>	<p>Current Impact Readiness Level: IRL 4 (Implementation) – throughout the use in the SCORE project, we aim to achieve IRL 5.</p> <p>Measures through to track the performance of the co-creation tool kit include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitors to co-creation tool pages (ENoLL & IHS) • Number of participants in the MOOC module • Post-event surveys (satisfaction)

4.1.2. KO 7.1: Synthesis of Socio-Economic Assessment Methods, Databases, And Studies Addressing Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA) And Other Adaptation Strategies.

Dissemination level: Public | **European/National Level or CCLL level Transfer:** European/National level

KO Description	
<p>Short Title</p>	<p>Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, databases, and studies addressing ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) and other adaptation strategies.</p>
<p>KO Description</p>	<p>This KO corresponds to a systematic literature review of scientific studies performing socio-economic assessments of climate change adaptation in coastal areas to determine which socioeconomic assessments were used most often.</p> <p>The review focused mainly on four types of adaptation strategies: hard (more relying on engineering-based solutions), soft (e.g., initiatives encouraging adaptation behaviour or focusing on coastal management and regulation), EBA (green-oriented measures more relying on interventions implemented at the ecosystem level), and hybrid (resulting from the mix of the previous solutions) adaptation strategies.</p> <p>The systematic literature review followed PRISMA - 51 studies were included in the literature review analysis. From these studies reviewed, 23 were cost-benefit analysis (CBA), six performed multicriteria analysis (MCA), three combined MCA and CBA, two developed a CBA</p>

	<p>and cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA), and the remaining 17 felt under the category of ‘other’ types of methods (e.g., real-option analysis - ROA; economic impact evaluation, and risk assessment).</p> <p>The review revealed that most of the selected studies addressed hybrid adaptation strategies.</p> <p>The analysis contributed towards a better understanding of the effectiveness, cost-efficiency, and generation of co-benefits by EbA solutions (e.g., provision of ecosystem services, support to livelihood, health), but it also stresses the need for further research on these topics.</p> <p>Conclusions of the literature review:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coastal areas are highly vulnerable to climate change and require appropriate climate adaptation strategies. • CBA or MCA are the most used socioeconomic assessment models. • Typically, these studies utilised hybrid adaptation strategies/solutions. • There is a need for decision-makers to conduct these types of adaptation strategies analysis when developing policies and plans.
Owner(s)	ENT, IHS, EnoLL and TERO
Readiness	Knowledge is ready for sharing; the article has been published in article has been accepted in MDPI (https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11020319)
Patent or other IPR	N/A

Knowledge Transfer Activity A

Target User Description: Academics

Target User identified as:	Academics working in the EBA sphere, including economists, sociologists, urban sustainability and climate change specialists, environmental scientists
Awareness: <i>Is the Target User aware of the KO already?</i>	The utilisation of EBAs is increasing, awareness of this specific KO would be limited.
Level of Understanding by target user: <i>What level of technical understanding does your Target User have of the surrounding topic?</i> <i>Does the KO need translation (from technical to layman’s terms)?</i> <i>Do they require training to take up the KO?</i>	Medium to high. There should be minimal need to educate academics who work within this field on how to utilise this KO as they have expertise in the field. The content is readable.
Role/Responsibility of Target Users:	To increase knowledge and ultimately utilisation of EBA techniques.

<p><i>What is the relevant role/responsibility of the Target User?</i></p>	
<p>Stakeholder Interest:</p>	<p>At this stage there have not been citations but there is growing interest and more research is needed on assessing the benefits and co-benefits that EbAs generate.</p>
<p>Knowledge Transfer Activities</p>	
<p>Message for Stakeholder</p>	<p>This KO could be applied to obtain a general overview of the different socio-economic assessment methods most frequently used to assess the economic performance of EbA and other adaptation strategies in local and regional coastal areas.</p> <p>This KO highlights the methods relying on stakeholder participation, the climate hazard and sectoral impact addressed by the method, and the adaptation solutions implemented. The KO presents the results of the different assessments in a way that is easily comparable to future research.</p>
<p>Channel/Activities</p> <p><i>i.e., Email, face-to-face, social media, active networks</i></p> <p><i>A more specific calendar of activities is available to the internal SCORE team.</i></p>	<p>Papers, academic conferences, lectures, stakeholder networks, and LinkedIn.</p>
<p>Knowledge Transfer Activity B</p>	
<p>Target User Description: Public sector decision-makers</p>	
<p>Target User identified as:</p>	<p>Public sector decision-makers, including city planning authorities, municipalities</p>
<p>Awareness:</p> <p><i>Is the Target User aware of the KO already?</i></p>	<p>Low: Decision-makers and planners presumably, have a low awareness of this KO.</p>
<p>Level of Understanding:</p> <p><i>What level of technical understanding does your Target User have of the surrounding topic? Does the KO need translation (from technical to layman's terms)? Do</i></p>	<p>Low-medium: Decision makers and planners will understand the deliverable and it would be highly relevant as it outlines different socioeconomic methods for the assessment of adaptation strategies/measures, including some of their pros and cons; provides information of a wide set of hard, soft, EBA and hybrid adaptation options; and summarises the main climate hazards affecting coastal areas, with flooding being the most studied.</p>

<i>they require training to take up the KO?</i>	
Role: <i>What is the relevant role/responsibility of the Target User?</i>	To implement climate adaptation strategies in their local municipality /region.
Interest:	Decision makers are increasingly being required (whether by policy mandates or the will of the people) to implement green(er) solutions in regard to climate adaptation, which also means conducting a socio-economic assessment in regards to the adaptation measures. This KO outlines the which socio-economic strategies are most commonly used and the co-benefits associated with EbA solutions.
Other Influences:	Political will and budgets play a significant role in the usability of this knowledge by public sector decision makers.
Knowledge Transfer Activities	
Message for Stakeholder: <i>Reasons why the knowledge is innovative, beneficial and, addresses the Target Users needs</i>	This KO could be applied to obtain a general overview of the different socio-economic assessment methods most frequently used to assess the economic performance of EbA and other adaptation strategies in local and regional coastal areas. Among others, this KO highlights the methods relying on stakeholder participation, the climate hazard and sectoral impact addressed by the method, and the adaptation solutions implemented. The KO presents the results of the different assessments in a way that is easily comparable to future research.
Channel/Activities <i>i.e., Email, face-to-face, social media, active networks</i> <i>A more specific calendar of activities is available to the internal SCORE team.</i>	Policy briefs to be developed in combination with future WP7 tasks (connection to future EBA research), webinar, and MOOC
Knowledge Transfer Evaluation	
Knowledge Transfer Activity: How do you plan to evaluate this Knowledge Transfer Activity?	Current Impact Readiness Level: IRL 1 (Conception) – throughout the use in the SCORE project, we aim to achieve IRL 2. Measures through which we can track the performance of the KO include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Number of policymakers the result is connected to. <input type="checkbox"/> Number of participants in the MOOC module <input type="checkbox"/> Number of citations

 Number of attendees to conference presentation

4.1.3. KO 7.2 - Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change

Dissemination level: Public | European/National Level or CCLL level Transfer: European/National level

KO Description	
Short Title	Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change
KO Description	<p>This KO corresponds to a set of methodological guidelines to evaluate EbA solutions through cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and multi-criteria analysis (MCA) in the CCLL of the project. The first part of the report associated with this KO introduces very briefly the CCLLs, describing the general characteristics of the study areas and the main climate hazards affecting them. Then, the different steps on how to implement MCA and a CBA are explained.</p> <p>MCA is more understandable for non-experts to implement and engage with, while CBA is highly technical and would require specific expertise (i.e., economist) to implement.</p>
Owner(s)	ENT, IHS, EnoLL and TERO
Readiness	This KO corresponds to SCORE's Deliverable 7.2 (Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change). This KO corresponds to an open access document, but the methods presented might be fine-tuned after testing and implementing the methodology in the SCORE CCLLs in Tasks 7.3 (Participatory socio-economic assessment of EbA interventions) and 7.4 (Expert-based socio-economic assessment of EbA interventions).
Patent or other IPR	N/A

Knowledge Transfer Activity A

Target User Description: Public Sector Decision-makers	
Target User identified as:	Some examples of the target list include planners, decision-makers, public authorities, city planning authorities, environmental departments.
Awareness: <i>Is the Target User aware of the KO already?</i>	Low: Based on the experiences with the CCLLs, the utilisation of the MCA/CBA methodology is rather limited in public sector settings, and thereby awareness would be lower.
Level of Understanding: <i>What level of technical understanding does your</i>	MCA is more understandable for non-experts to implement and engage with, while CBA is highly technical and would require specific expertise (i.e., economist) to implement.

<p><i>Target User have of the surrounding topic?</i></p> <p><i>Does the KO need translation (from technical to layman's terms)?</i></p> <p><i>Do they require training to take up the KO?</i></p>	<p>The KO (in the deliverable form) is relatively easy to understand once it has been explained, but ultimately, they would require someone with domain-level expertise to implement it.</p>
<p>Role:</p> <p><i>What is the relevant role/responsibility of the Target User?</i></p>	<p>In the overall goal of implementing EBAs, the public sector decision-makers are the ones who are ultimately paying and deciding on the implementation of EBAs.</p>
<p>Interest:</p>	<p>While EBAs are becoming more and more popular, largely the interest in the methodology will depend regionally. For those communities with an interest in EBAs, the methodology can support their decision-making process, including both stakeholder perspectives and a more technical assessment.</p>
<p>Other Influences:</p> <p><i>Who else could be influencing the Target User's decisions?</i></p> <p><i>Do they have the authority to apply your knowledge? If not, who does and how can you access this person?</i></p>	<p>Public opinion & governance/voting cycles ultimately impact the ability to implement EBAs and therefore use this methodology. Particularly the MCA methodology requires these decision-makers to value the perspectives of the quadruple helix.</p>
<p>Knowledge Transfer Activities</p>	
<p>Message for Stakeholder:</p> <p><i>Reasons why the knowledge is innovative, beneficial and, addresses the Target Users needs</i></p>	<p>Decision makers, city planning authorities, and municipalities could use the CBA and MCA methods to evaluate and decide on the most cost-effective and/or most preferred adaptation interventions to implement. These tools should be used as part of the decision process when planning adaptation strategies to climate change. The participatory-based nature of an MCA allows to incorporate the perceptions of different stakeholders about the studied adaptation measures (e.g., citizens and citizens' groups; academia; NGOs; private sector; public administration).</p> <p>The application of the CBA and MCA methods could result in a better understanding and evaluation of different types of (already implemented, planned, or hypothetical) EbA analysed alone or in comparison with other types of adaptation strategies (e.g., hard, soft). The use of both methods would allow to obtain an evaluation of different measures from a cost-efficiency perspective, but also in relation to the potential contribution towards other non-market benefits (e.g., air quality improvement, increased biodiversity, improved livelihood).</p>
<p>Channels / Activities</p>	<p>Policy briefs and conference presentations</p>

<p><i>A more specific calendar of activities is available to the internal SCORE team.</i></p>	
<p>Knowledge Transfer Activity B</p>	
<p>Target User Description: General Public & civil society organisations (CSO)</p>	
<p>Target User identified as:</p>	<p>General public, particularly those in the CCLL locations.</p> <p>Note: these specific activities are about raising awareness of EBAs, in the hopes of supporting the utilisation of the methodologies presented in this KO.</p>
<p>Awareness: <i>Is the Target User aware of the KO already?</i></p>	<p>Generally, there is a lack of awareness of EBAs, however, with an ever-increasing knowledge of climate change and communities actively feeling the effects of the climate crisis, there is an increasing receptivity towards these solutions.</p>
<p>Level of Understanding: <i>What level of technical understanding does your Target User have of the surrounding topic?</i> <i>Does the KO need translation (from technical to layman's terms)?</i> <i>Do they require training to take up the KO?</i></p>	<p>Some education is needed to explain both the idea of EBAs, but the co-currently, the idea that these can be co-created and locally embedded would need to be taught.</p>
<p>Role: <i>What is the relevant role/responsibility of the Target User?</i></p>	<p>The general public and more importantly, CSOs can play a massive role in putting appropriate pressure on the public authorities/decision-makers, if they are educated about their options.</p>
<p>Interest:</p>	<p>Whilst the general public and civil society are large groups with diversity within, there are certain climate activists and climate change affected-people due to various climatic hazards (i.e., heat waves, coastal erosion, etc.) with a high interest in EBAs.</p>
<p>Knowledge Transfer Activities</p>	
<p>Message for Stakeholder: <i>Reasons why the knowledge is innovative, beneficial and, addresses the Target Users needs</i></p>	<p>Focusing broadly on the ideas of EBAs & co-creation, we want to encourage citizens to be actively involved in their local environmental decision-making and their community's future.</p> <p>Key Message: Ecosystem-based approaches matter to the public because they provide sustainable solutions to climate challenges, safeguard biodiversity, and enhance climate resilience. By preserving natural ecosystems like wetlands and forests, we can mitigate climate impacts, protect against extreme weather events, and ensure cost-effective solutions compared to traditional infrastructure. Sustainable resource management and community well-being are also benefits, as these approaches support clean water, air, and</p>

	recreation opportunities. Embracing these approaches empowers us to build a resilient and harmonious future, benefiting both nature and human society.
Channel/Activities <i>i.e., Email, face-to-face, social media, active networks</i> <i>A more specific calendar of activities is available to the internal SCORE team.</i>	Amplify the CCLLs as a local case study (could be presented in local media), local science events, social media, podcasts, and community forums. MOOC, Local media, schools, social media, podcasts, and community forums.
Knowledge Transfer Activity C	
Target User Description: EU Projects & Academics	
Target User identified as:	Economists, sociologists, urban sustainability and climate change specialists, environmental scientists and related projects
Awareness: <i>Is the Target User aware of the KO already?</i>	Medium to high
Level of Understanding: <i>What level of technical understanding does your Target User have of the surrounding topic?</i> <i>Does the KO need translation (from technical to layman's terms)?</i> <i>Do they require training to take up the KO?</i>	High – as domain experts, this should be easy for them to understand.
Role/Responsibility of Target Users: <i>What is the relevant role/responsibility of the Target User?</i>	To conduct research on the topics of EBAs, climate adaptation and socioeconomic assessments.
Interest:	High - Economists, sociologists, urban sustainability and climate change specialists, and environmental scientists could run the assessment of the different adaptation options and communicate the results to decision-makers and authorities for them to consider within their planning strategies.
Knowledge Transfer Activities	

<p>Message for Stakeholder</p> <p><i>Reasons why the knowledge is innovative, beneficial and, addresses the Target Users needs</i></p>	<p>The application of the CBA and MCA methods could result in a better understanding and evaluation of different types of (already implemented, planned, or hypothetical) EbA analysed alone or in comparison with other types of adaptation strategies (e.g., hard, soft). The use of both methods would allow to obtain an evaluation of different measures from a cost-efficiency perspective, but also in relation to the potential contribution towards other non-market benefits (e.g., air quality improvement, increased biodiversity, improved livelihood).</p>
<p>Channel/Activities</p> <p><i>i.e., Email, face-to-face, social media, active networks</i></p> <p><i>A more specific calendar of activities is available to the internal SCORE team.</i></p>	<p>Use the CCLLs case studies, conferences, publications, European project events (i.e., Bauhaus), Horizon Magazine</p>
<p>Knowledge Transfer Evaluation</p>	
<p>Knowledge Transfer Activity: How do you plan to evaluate this Knowledge Transfer Activity?</p>	<p>Current Impact Readiness Level: IRL 1 (Conception) – throughout the use in the SCORE project, we aim to achieve IRL 2.</p> <p>Measures through which we can track the performance of the KO include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Number of policymakers the result is connected to/number of meetings with key policymakers regarding the KO <input type="checkbox"/> Number of participants in the MOOC module <input type="checkbox"/> Number of citations <input type="checkbox"/> Number of attendees to conference presentation <input type="checkbox"/> Number of downloads/views of the policy brief <input type="checkbox"/> Number of engagements related to Horizon Magazine <input type="checkbox"/> Number of engagement activities (i.e., number of podcasts, number of local media activities, engagement at schools) <input type="checkbox"/> Social media followers

5. CONCLUSIONS

The first two phases of the project (initial awareness phase and target dissemination phase) have been successfully conducted with the support of all SCORE partners. The project has reached a very satisfactory level of visibility, even gathering attention from the EU Mission Adaptation to Climate Change.

A diverse range of activities in the CCLLs have involved a variety of stakeholders (citizens, students, policymakers, businesses, local authorities).

During the second phase, further efforts were specifically made to increase dissemination at local and regional level and more closely monitor the activities implemented by the CCLLs. The WP9 team also produced more video content, organised additional webinars, and was very active on social media, ensuring wide dissemination through various networks. Additional resources were developed to ensure the dissemination of project materials, including the use of GeoStories on the SCORE platform. Through knowledge collection, a total of 16 KOs have been collected, and associated KTPs for prioritised KERs were developed and monitored, and associated tailored communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities took place.

The main priority in the final year of the project will be to ensure the proper dissemination and exploitation of all project outputs and maximise the project's impacts and legacy towards a large range of stakeholders at local, national and European level. Several important activities are already scheduled (e.g., Workshop at the EU Week of Regions and Cities), while other are still in preparation (e.g., Final SCORE infoday, final brochure, MOOCs, Policy briefs). Partners are all well involved in the process, and will continue to regularly participate in events, publish scientific papers, collaborate with local stakeholders, etc.

In the final year, all remaining knowledge will undergo collection, and subsequently, knowledge transfer plans for all KERs will be developed and implementation of said plans will proceed until project period closes. WP9 works closely with the CCLLs and other work packages, such as WP2, WP6, WP7, and WP8, to ensure maximum impact of SCORE results. WP9 will ensure appropriate communication, exploitation, and dissemination activities tailored to such knowledge to ensure the maximum, long-lasting impact of the SCORE project.

6. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 – COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION STRATEGY GUIDELINES FOR CCLLS

Introduction

Developing a communication strategy is an essential part of connecting with your key stakeholders in the most efficient and effective manner. The strategy will differ depending on the communication goal and the stakeholders your CCLL is trying to target.

Communication Strategy

When developing your communication strategy, it is essential that these 8 actions are completed:

1. Do an **initial brainstorm** on what your CCLL needs/wants to communicate/disseminate:
 - What is the end goal? Who are trying to reach? What are your timelines?
2. Define your **goal** → what are you aiming to achieve by implementing this communication strategy?
 - Examples of potential goals:
 1. Increase awareness and visibility of the CCLL to the general public.
 2. Share research and associated outputs with local municipalities.
 3. Build relationships with industry stakeholders to share (future) project learnings.
 4. Drive people to the website and other SCORE materials.
 5. Ensure key attendees at a CCLL workshop
3. Who are the **stakeholders**?
 - Be as specific as possible – focus on those stakeholders identified in your POP. i.e., policy makers, city planners, general populations, community activists, academics, youth groups etc.
4. What **communication method** is best to utilise?
 - Remember not every communication activity needs to be a big social media presentation. Depending on your time and goals, setting coffee meetings with the most relevant stakeholders can be the most useful. Communication methods include, but are not limited to, emails, eNewsletters, Presentations (online or physical), Meetings/phone calls, Events, Social Media. See the pros and cons below.
5. What is your **key message**?
 - Develop a clear key message – make sure the language choices match the needs and expectations of your key stakeholder group.
6. Set your **timeline**:
 - Adjust your timeline depending on when your goal needs to be met.
 - Goals built around social media require more time to develop and see the needed response. Personal phone calls and emails will require a shorter time frame. However, no matter what the case, give the target groups time to commit/agree to your goals.

- Think about the key moments to capitalise – can you align your goals with a larger movement (i.e., EU Green Week, World Water Day, Earth Day, local environment/science events, etc.)
7. **Implement** the strategy
 - Who on your team is going to do this?
 - Set important dates (milestones) about what needs to be done, by when, who facilitates, who is involved, who is affected etc.
 - Use the communication strategy template (see below) to track activities and progress.
 8. **Evaluate** your success
 - Was the goal accomplished? Reflect on what went well and what could be improved for next time.

The Basics – Checklist

1. Double check that your key message matches your stakeholder.
2. Remember the logistics:
 - a. How will you reach the stakeholder - do you have their email(s), social media profile(s), phone number, etc.?
 - b. Assign responsibility - Who on the CCLL team will be reaching out? Who will be following up?
 - c. What is your timeline?
3. For dissemination materials, have you included the EC disclaimer text?

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4. Do you need support from WP9? Euronovia should be aware of all communication activities.

Communication Tools – Pros & Cons

The below table provides an overview of different communication tools, their function and general pros/cons from the perspective of a small entity, like a CCLL. This list is not exhaustive but can provide a starting point.

Tool	Use	Pros	Cons
“Face to Face” – Most Personal			
Face to Face meetings	Discuss specific details and activities with small groups of key stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most effective form of communication • Very personal • Can be used to discuss sensitive topic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires travel • Can be more time consuming • Time is required to build report with stakeholders.
Phone Calls/ Video Calls	Discuss specific details and activities with smaller groups of key stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A personal form of communication. • Easy to assess the stakeholders needs • Eliminates time travel • Can be used to discuss sensitive topics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time is required to build report with stakeholders.

Events/ Conferences	Connecting with like-minded individuals/projects in a personal and interactive environment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal connection • An excellent way to promote your CCLL to individuals who are thematically interested but otherwise unaware. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time consuming • Can be costly (travel, materials, registration, etc.)
Digital, but personal			
Emails	Share events & materials, discuss CCLL details and upcoming activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy and convenient • Provides a “paper trail” • Can reach multiple stakeholders simultaneously 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can lack personalisation • Our message can get lost in the sea of emails.
Webinars	Best used to communicate a message or learning outcome to a large group.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A captive audience for a set period of time. • Virtual audience provides the opportunity to share project learnings/CCLL outputs virtually to a large group of people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time consuming to put together • Marketing effort is required to get attendees.
Social Media & Mass e-Mails – Most Wide Reaching			
eNewsletter (Blogs)	Sharing specific learnings, events, or any CCLL news with a wide variety of stakeholders. Language used should be simple to reach a wide audience.	Allows easy sharing of the CCLLs activities and news. As a CCLL, you “own” your mailing list (as opposed to Twitter, where you do not “own” your following list).	Requires building a mailing list, which can be time consuming. Mass emails can lack a personal touch and can end up in a spam folder. Mailing lists need to be GDPR compliant.
Twitter	Sharing micro-updates (CCLL updates, news articles, events, learnings, etc.) primarily with the general public, decision makers and activists.	Useful for keeping the general public and community aware of the day to day actions of the CCLL. Can be used to connect with larger social movements (i.e., Earth Day or Green Week). Twitter keeps an organised list of “followers” Can personally connect with the community/key stakeholders.	Tweets have a short lifespan, so content is needed consistently.
LinkedIn	Sharing longer updates, (CCLL updates, blogs, news articles, events, learnings, etc.) primarily with academics and other professionals.	Useful for keeping academics and professional colleagues aware of the day to day actions of the CCLL. Can be used to connect with larger social movements (i.e., Earth Day or Green Week).	Audience base is primarily limited to academics or industry stakeholders. Time consuming to maintain.

		Can identify specific stakeholders/decision makers in relevant institutions.	
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Knowledge Transfer Strategy Template

#	Title	Objectives and Goals	Key Stakeholders	Messaging and Content	Required Actions	Communication Tools	Urgency	Due Date	Responsible Person	Other Notes
1										
2										
3										
4										
5										
6										
7										
8										
9										
10										

Social Media Strategic Guidelines

Posting and Sharing Content: Driving project awareness and engagement can be facilitated through a variety of activities, most notably through:

- Sharing Content – i.e., news articles, events, publications, photos, anecdotes, commentary
- Retweeting, Liking, Sharing Content
- Creating a continually engaging “project persona”.
- Create an online community with likeminded projects, professionals, and agencies

It is important to use plain English: simple but to the point, optimistic, focus on the benefit for society, it should be accessible, not full of complex jargon, nice pictures, with a good use of emojis. It is important clearly explain the project and our outputs in a way that people unfamiliar with project will understand.

Stakeholders: Review your key stakeholders identified in the POP, which are more relevant to be approached via social media? Consider that social media is best used to reach a large number of more general stakeholders.

Key Performance Indicators: A Key Performance Indicator is a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively a company is achieving objectives. Your CCLL could track likes, overall engagement, followers’ growth. KPI’s allow us to assess whether we are reaching our target audiences and how engaged the users are with the content.

Planning a Campaign: A campaign is a promotion style that is separate to the continuous online engagement used to promote a specific activity, event, or output of the project. Below is the procedure followed when organising

these campaigns. As the CCLL continues to grow and more results are available, these campaigns will become more tailored to specific stakeholder groups.

Step 1: Conduct a Situation Analysis

When planning a campaign, the first step is a situational analysis to have a better understanding of the context in which your campaign will sit. The situational analysis should include a thorough analysis of your target audience (who, why, how you're going to target them) and how you will measure performance (KPIs).

Before delivering on a specific campaign, consider:

- Who is our target audience for this project?
- What creative messaging has been used to date? What worked, what did not? Did a specific tactic perform poorly (i.e., no one clicked a link attached to a post)? Refer to analytics as to what posts and tactics performed well and what performed poorly.
- Resources/capabilities/constraints? What platforms do we have access to? Can partners help through their socials? What freedom do we have? What is our budget?
- The situation analysis should contain a thorough analysis of:
 - **Target audience:** Who will they be? Who do we want to hear our messages?
 - **Visibility:** How can we stand out/cut through? There is competition for project visibility.
 - **Previous performance/results:** Using back-end social media analytics such as Twitter Analytics, insights from previous campaigns can be used to improve future campaigns.

Step 2: Identifying Target Audiences

Next consider who is your ideal and intended audience for this interaction. Consider the following:

- **Demographics:** Levels of education, diversity of age, race, experiences with the healthcare system, etc.
- **Geographics:** Should it target researchers, healthcare systems etc. in specific country/area?
- **Relationship with CCLL:** Will the audience stay interested beyond this campaign? Will you create a new target audience/expand on an existing one?
- **Behaviour:** Why does this audience visit the website/social media?
- **Target audience profile:** Make a fictitious persona to represent your audience. Try to imagine if this person saw your project would it interest them? Would they understand the lingo? Would they engage? What would make this person visit again?

Step 3: Objective-Setting

Set achievable objectives. It is recommended to focus on raising awareness of the project to the relevant target audience. In time, these can then be expanded into more analytical objectives when socials are more established.

Examples:

- Twitter account currently has 34 Followers, objective is to increase following to 100 followers before 1st of November 2020.
- Boost engagement rate on posts from X to X over a period of 1 month.
- Increase awareness of CCLL on Twitter by increasing reach and impressions by X.

Step 4: Strategy & Tactics

Strategy is the big picture. It summarizes how you're going to get there. Your objectives, tactics, scheduling and overall plan is your strategy. Consider:

- What activities are required to accomplish your objectives?
- What to say? (message/content)
- How to say it? (Execution, tone, creative strategy)
- Where to say it? (Social media)
- When? (timing)
- What do we wish to achieve?

Step 5: Campaign Evaluation

Ensure the campaign is evaluated following the completion to ensure that the campaign and activities are justifying a sufficient outcome. If this campaign was not sufficiently successful, consider what risk mitigation/contingency planning can be taken in future to adjust.

Evaluations can consider the following:

- During and after-effects.
- Changes in knowledge, attitudes, behaviour.
- Changes in metric (changes in number of followers, website visits, video views, twitter impressions, etc.)
- Target audience relationships.
- Publicity
- Basic Metrics & Insights

Social Media Jargon

- **Impressions:** How often your post or ad is shown. An impression is counted each time your it is shown.
- **Reach:** Number of people who received impressions of a post. (Number of unique people who saw your content).
- **Organic Reach:** Number of people who saw your content for free. (You didn't spend money for the post to be seen, appeared on newsfeeds of followers).
- **Paid Reach:** Number of people who saw your post as a result of promotion. Influenced by ad spend. (But this needs to be done wisely i.e. targeting).
- **Engagement:** When people perform actions on your content. Like, comment, click post, react, share. Number of people engaged with the post divided by number of people who were reached. Example if you had 10 likes on a post and it reached 100 people, engagement rate is 10%.
- **KPI:** Key Performance Indicator. A measurable value that demonstrates how effectively a company is achieving objectives. i.e. Likes, Engagement, Followers growth are KPIs.
- **Call to Action (C2A):** Phrase that's used to tell the user exactly what action to take and how to take it. Prompt an immediate response/compel an audience to act in a specific way.
- **Conversion rate:** The % of visitors who take the action you want them to take

ANNEX 2 – PRIORITISED CCLL STAKEHOLDERS

List of Identified Stakeholders in Each CCLL		
Benidorm Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Locals	Benidorm Neighbourhood Association [Asociación de vecinos Benidorm]	Civil Society
	Area Ingeneriera Civil del Ayuntamiento [Town Hall Civil Engineering Area]	Government
	Town Hall Beach Area [Areas playes del ayuntamiento]	Government
	Local Police of Benidorm	Government
	Climate Intelligence [Inteligencia Climatica]	Industry
	Dinapsis	Academic
	Smart Office (Distrito Digital)	Government
	Tour Operators	Industry
	Visit Benidorm (Tourism Board)	Industry
	Benidorm Marina	Industry
Regional	RA Beaches Concessionaire [Concesionaria Playas]	Industry
	Chance/Choice (Benidorm Merchants Association)	Industry
	Hidraqua (Water Company)	Industry
National	UA Dept of Engineering	Academic
	UA: Department of Technology, Information Technology and Computation	Academic
	Pedro Zaragoza Orts Chair of Tourism Studies	Academic
	General Directorate of Coasts [Dirección General de Costas]	Government
	HOSBEC (Hotel and Tourism Business Association)	Industry
Dublin Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	University College Dublin	Academic
	Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council	Government
	Smart Dún Laoghaire (Innovation Collaborator Group)	Government
	Dún Laoghaire Education and Training Board	Academic
	Dún Laoghaire Men's Shed (Health Club)	Civil Society
	Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown Public Participation Network (NGO)	Civil Society
	Dún Laoghaire Business Association	Industry
	Dún Laoghaire Further Education Institute (DFEi)	Academic

	Techworks Marine Dún Laoghaire	Industry
	Dún Laoghaire primary and secondary schools (multiple)	Civil society
	Tidy Towns	Civil society
	Dún Laoghaire Enterprise Centre	Industry
Regional	Local Authority Waters Programme (LAWPRO)	
	Iarnrod Éireann [Irish Rail]	Industry
	Dublin Bay Biosphere Partnership	Government
National	An Taisce Environmental Education Unit (NGO)	Civil Society
	ECO / UNESCO Ireland (Environmental Education and Youth Organisation)	Civil Society
	Office of Public Works (OPW)	Government
	Microsoft Education & CSR	Industry
	Geological Survey Ireland (GSI)	Government
	Irish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)	Government
	Friends of the Earth (Environmental Organisation)	Civil Society
	Irish Research Councils New Foundation (Research Funding Programme)	Civil Society
	Rethink Ireland (Non-Profit Support Charity)	Civil Society
	Sensor Provider Companies / DANALTO	Industry
	Telecommunication / Virgin Media & Vodafone	Industry
Gdansk Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	University of Gdansk, Department of Physical Geography and Environmental Management	Academic
	Geography Teachers	Civil Society
	Teachers from Schools for Disabled People	Civil Society
	Kindergarten School Teachers	Civil Society
	Neighbours Societies [Rady Sąsiedzkie]	Civil Society
	Gdansk Development Office [Biuro Rozwoju Gdańska]	Government
	Municipal Office of Gdansk, Department of the Environment	Government
	Port of Gdansk	Government
	Saur Neptun Sewage Company	Government
	Eko-Konsult (Technical and Environmental Consultancy)	Industry
	Port of Gdansk, Environmental Protection	Industry
	Pro Digital	Industry
	RMAAG Foundation	Industry

	Hevelianum (Educational Science Centre)	Civil Society
	Gdansk Infrastructure [Melioracje Gdańskie]	Government
	Gdansk Road and Greenery Management [Zarząd Dróg i Zieleni]	Government
	University for elderly people	Civil Society
	Tourism Cluster	Industry
Regional	Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection	Government
	RZGW - Regional Panel for Water Management	Government
	Tri-city Landscape Park [Trójmiejski Park Krajobrazowy]	Government
	Water Gdansk	Government
	Marine Institute	Academic
	Maritime Office	Government
	Operational Center for Flood Protection, Regional Water Management Board	Government
	Voivodeship Crisis Management [Wojewódzkie Centrum Zarządzania Kryzysowego]	Government
National	Education Schoolboard [Kuratorium Oświaty]	Government
	Energa (Energy Distribution Company)	Government
	Institute for Meteorology and Water Management	Government
	Polish Academy of Science	Academic
	National Forests [Lasy Państwowe]	Government
	Operational Centre - Flooding Protection [Centrum Operacyjne Ochrony Przeciwpowodziowej]	Government
Massa Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	Istituto Istruzione Superiore Meucci di Massa	Academic
	Paladini Apuo-versiliesi (Environmental Association)	Civil Society
	Municipality of Massa	Government
	Ageparc - Massa Camping Association - [Associazione Campeggi Massa]	Civil Society
	Apuan Weather Meteorologists [Meteo Apuane]	Civil Society
	Club Alpino Italiano (CAI) Massa (Cultural Center)	Civil Society
	Fondo Ambiente Italiano (FAI) (Italian Environment Fund)	Civil Society
	Italia Nostra	Civil Society
	Legambiente Massa-Montignoso (Environmental Association)	Civil Society
	Magliano Massa Fishermen's Club - [Circolo dei Pescatori del Magliano Massa]	Civil Society
	Pro Loco (tourist associations)	Civil Society
	Rotaract Club Massa Carrara	Civil Society

	Rotary Club Carrara e Massa	Civil Society
	Scout AGESCI gruppo Lu.Ma.Ca	Civil Society
	Sub Alto Tirreno Center Amateur Sports Association	Civil Society
	WWF Massa (Environmental Association)	Civil Society
	ARPAT	Government
	Authority of Bacino	Government
	Carrara Municipality	Government
	Montignoso Municipality	Government
	Municipal Union	Government
	Port Authority	Government
	Province of Massa Carrara	Government
	Consorzio di Bonifica Toscana Nord	Industry
	Associazione Balneari Compagnia del Mare	Industry
	CIA (Confederazione Italiana Agricoltori) Massa Carrara	Industry
	CNA Balneari	Industry
	Coldiretti Massa	Industry
	Confcommercio (Merchant Association)	Industry
	Confesercenti (Merchant Association)	Industry
	Consorzio Riviera Apuana (Bathing Association)	Industry
	Federalberghi (Association of Hoteliers)	Industry
	FIAIP (Estate Professional Order)	Industry
	Ordine degli Architetti di Massa Carrara (Professional Order)	Industry
	Ordine degli Ingegneri di Massa Carrara (Professional Order)	Industry
	Ordine dei geologi della Toscana (Professional Order)	Industry
	Ordine dei Geometri di Massa Carrara (Professional Order)	Industry
	Camera di Commercio di Massa-Carrara (NGO)	Industry
	Civil Protection Associations [Associazioni Protezione Civile] Misericordia	Civil Society
	Civil Protection Associations [Associazioni Protezione Civile] Pubblica Assistenza	Civil Society
	Civil Protection Associations [Associazioni Protezione Civile] VAB (Volontari Antincendio Boschivo)	Civil Society
Regional	Consorzio LaMMA	Academic
	Tuscany Region Settore Difesa del Suolo	Academic
National	National Research Council of Italy - Institute of atmospheric sciences and climate (ISAC CNR)	Academic

	National Research Council of Italy- Institute of BioEconomy (IBE CNR)	Academic
	National Research Council of Italy - Institute of Marine Sciences (ISMAR CNR)	Academic
	University of Florence Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra	Academic
	University of Pisa Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra	Academic
Oarsoaldea Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	Don Bosco - Vocational training school	Government
	Public Schools - Primary and Secondary	Government
	Albaola - Sea Culture Factory	Civil Society
	MATER - Ecoactive Museum Ship	Civil Society
	Public Summer Camps	Government
	Itxaszerbi (Local Ferry company)	Industry
	Arditurri Mines	Civil Society
	Buceo Donosti - Submariners (sports)	Civil Society
	Energy Community of Errenteria	Civil Society
	Energy Community of Oiartzun	Civil Society
	Labore Oarso (Food Association)	Civil Society
	Iratzerri - Sustainability & Energy Association	Civil Society
	Rowing Associations	Civil Society
	Blas de Lezo - Vocational training school	Government
	Tknika - Vocational training school	Government
	Lasa Naval	Industry
	Pasaiaiko Arrantzaleen Kofradia (Fishermen's Association)	Industry
	Auzoetako Elkarteak (Neighbourhood association)	Civil Society
	Local government (4 municipalities)	Government
	Oarsoaldea Development Agency Management Board, communications and tourism departments	Government
Berdabio Basogintza	Industry	
Regional	AZTI - Marine Science & Technology	Government
	BC3 - Basque Centre for Climate Change	Government
	EHU/UPV - University of Basque Country	Government
	Ados - Environmental Consulting	Industry
	Izadi 21 - Environment Consulting	Industry

Sangalli, Coronel y Asociados, S.L. - EBA Expert Company	Industry
Ekolur - Environment Consulting	Industry
Asmatu - Engineering company	Industry
Capital Energy	Industry
Naider - Environment Consulting	Industry
Eguzki (E-NGO)	Civil Society
Ekologistak Martxan (E-NGO)	Civil Society
Juventud por el Clima (E-NGO)	Civil Society
Lurguia (E-NGO)	Civil Society
Surfrider (E-NGO)	Civil Society
Aranzadi Zientzia Elkarteak - Science Association	Government
CEDEX - Public Works Studies & Experimentation	Government
CEIT	Government
Elhuyar - Advanced Knowledge Application	Government
MU - Mondragon University	Government
Tecnalia - Science & Technology	Government
TECNUN	Government
University of Cantabria - Instituto de Hidráulica	Government
University of Deusto	Government
ACLIMA - Environment Cluster	Industry
Euskal Herriko Itsas Foroa - Marine Cluster	Industry
GAIA Applied Knowledge and Technology Cluster	Industry
GoiEner - Energy company	Industry
Innobasque	Industry
Itsas Garapen Elkarteak	Industry
Predictia	Industry
SUDS - Sistemas Urbanos de Drenaje Sostenible	Industry
Tourism Cluster	Industry
Añarbeko Urak (Water Management Company)	Industry
Eusko Jaurlaritzak - Basque Country government BASQUETOUR - Tourism Agency	Government
Eusko Jaurlaritzak - Basque Country government Emergency & Meteorology Manag./Euskalmet Meteo. Agency	Government
Eusko Jaurlaritzak - Basque Country government EVE - Energy Agency	Government

	Eusko Jaurlaritza - Basque Country government SPRI - Business Development Agency	Government
	Eusko Jaurlaritza - Basque Country government URA - Water Agency (riverside)	Government
	Gipuzkoako Foru Aldundia (province government) Environmental Department	Government
	IHOBE - Environmental Agency	Government
	Ministry of Economy Consorcio de Compensación de Seguros	Government
	Ministry of Environment Servicio Provincial de Costas de Gipuzkoa	Government
	Ministry of Transport and Mobility Pasaia Port authority	Government
	Naturklima - Climate Change Foundation	Government
	ZinCo	Industry
National	Euroregion/ Euroeskualdea (cross border European Agency)	Government
Oeiras Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	Local Citizens	Civil Society
	Geography Teachers	Civil Society
	Students from Elementary Public Schools	Civil Society
	Civil Protection, Oeiras Municipality (CMPC)	Government
	Communication Department, Oeiras Municipality (GC)	Government
	Department of Education, Oeiras Municipality (DE)	Government
	Department of Municipality Construction (DOM)	Government
	DOT MO	Government
	Environmental Department, Oeiras Municipality (DGA)	Government
	Firemen corporations: CBV Algés	Government
	Firemen corporations: CBV Dafundo	Government
	Firemen corporations: CBV Oeiras	Government
	Firemen corporations: CBV Paço de Arcos	Government
	Firemen corporations: Barcarena	Government
	Firemen corporations: Carnaxide	Government
	Oeiras Municipality	Government
	Strategy for Science & Technology, Oeiras Municipality (GCI)	Government
	Territorial Intelligence Office (GIT)	Government
	Miraflores School [Agrupamento de Escolas Miraflores]	Civil society
	Oeiras Viva - Gestão de Equipamentos Culturais e Desportivos, E.M.	Government
Carnaxide School [Agrupamento de Escolas Carnaxide - Escola Camilo Castelo Branco]	Civil society	

	Sensor Company	Industry
Regional	Authority of Lisbon Port (APL) [Administração do Porto de Lisboa, S.A.]	Government
	Intermunicipality Water and Sanitation Facilities (SIMAS)	Government
	Lisbon Metropolitan Area (AML)	Government
	Regional Development Commission of Lisboa and Tagus Valley [CCDRLVT]	Government
	Social Action Department [Departamento Ação Social]	Government
	Commercial and Business Association of the Municipalities of Oeiras and Amadora	Industry
	Lisboa E-Nova - [Agência de Energia e Ambiente de Lisboa]	Industry
	CODIS: Comandante Operacional Distrital de Lisboa	Government
	Lisboa Gás, S.A. (Gas Company)	Industry
National	ITQB (Research Institute)	Academic
	Atlantic-University Higher Institution	Academic
	IST-ID (Research Institution)	Academic
	Portuguese Environment Agency [Agencia Portuguesa do Ambiente (APA)]	Government
	Portuguese Sea and Atmosphere Institute [Instituto Portugues Mar e Atmosfera]	Government
	Carris (Transportation Company)	Industry
	E-redes (Grid Company)	Industry
	Firsrule (Engineering Company)	Industry
	Fundação INATEL (Foundation)	Industry
	Hotel Vila Galé Collection Palácio dos Arcos	Industry
	General Management of the Maritime Authority [Direção Geral da Autoridade Marítima]	Government
	Faculty of Human Motricity [Faculdade de Motricidade Humana]	Academic
	ICS (Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon (ICS-UL))	Academic
	LNEC- Departamento de Estruturas (LNEC - Nucleo de Estuários e Zonas Costeiras)	Academic
	Police authorities [Polícia de Segurança Pública]	Government
	Infrastructures Portugal	Industry
Piran Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	Local Secondary School	Civil Society
	Local Primary School	Civil Society
	Local Historians	Civil Society
	Piran Municipality	Government
	Public Space and Waste Management Service	Government

	Civil Governance Groups	Civil Society
	Elected City Council Representatives	Civil Society
	Local Civil Protection Service	Government
	Municipal Environmental Office	Government
	Local Hotels	Industry
	Local Tour Guides	Industry
	Civil Initiative Group	Civil society
	Cultural Heritage Museum and Local/Regional Archives	Industry
	Italian Community Minority Group	Civil Society
	Municipal Waste Management and Ecologic Manager	Government
	Piran Community Group	Civil society
	Fishery Community Members	Civil Society
	Municipal Civil Working Body for Spatial Planning	Government
	Local Restaurants & Cafe Owners	Industry
Regional	Local Public Cultural Heritage Administration	Academic
	Public Water Supply Company	Industry
	Interdisciplinary Research Organisation	Academic
	Nature Reserve Management	Academic
	For-profit Firm Providing Innovation in Sustainability Sector	Industry
National	National Civil Protection Administration	Government
	National Environmental Agency	Government
	For-profit Firm Providing Innovation in Sustainability Sector (Rain Gardens)	Industry
	National Water Management Administration	Government
Samsun Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	Istanbul Technical University	Academic
	KTO Karatay University	Academic
	Mersin University	Academic
	Ondokuz Mavis University	Academic
	Samsun University	Academic
	Farmers of the Kızılırmak Delta	Civil Society
	OMYEGDER (Ondokuzmayis Local Action Community)	Civil Society
	Ondokuzmayis Public Education Center	Civil Society

	Yorukler Fishermen Co.	Civil Society
	Ondokuzmayis Municipality	Government
	Samsun Governorship	Government
	Samsun Municipality	Government
	British American Tobacco	Industry
	ISTECHSOFT Company	Industry
	YEDAS Energy Company	Industry
	Local Primary School Students	Civil Society
Regional	International Innovation Association (UIDER)	Civil Society
	Samsun Provincial Directorate of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change	Government
	State Hydraulic Works Samsun Office	Government
	Başakşehir Living Lab	Civil Society
	Provincial Directorate of National Education	Government
	Disaster And Emergency Management Presidency	Government
	Turkish State Meteorological Service Samsun Office	Government
Sligo Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	ATU (Sustainability, Ecology)	Academic
	Locals from community groups in Coney Island, Dunmoran, Streedagh, Rosses Point, Enniscrone, Raghly	Civil Society
	Tidy Towns - Sligo	Civil Society
	Local Church Groups	Civil Society
	Coast Care Group	Civil Society
	Clean Coast Road Show	Civil Society
	Environmental Youth Group (Sligo Youth Assembly)	Civil Society
	GAA Clubs	Civil Society
	Sligo Sport and Recreation Partnerships (SSRP)	Civil Society
	Summerhill School	Civil Society
	Tourists visiting the SCORE locations	Civil Society
	Enniscrone primary and secondary schools	Civil Society
	Local surf clubs	Civil Society
	Elected Council Officials, City/Public Offices	Government
	Sligo County Council	Government

	Sligo Chamber of Commerce	Industry
	Sligo SEC	Industry
Regional	Archaeologists and Historians (misme, Cexis, Heritage Officer Sligo)	Academic
	Irish Language and Place Name Experts	Academic
	Public Participation Networks (PPN)	Civil Society
	Sustainable Energy Communities (SEC) Network	Civil Society
	Climate Action Regional Office - CARO	Government
National	Marine Institutes	Academic
	Sand Dune Ecologist (Expert) NPWS	Academic
	Clean Coast - an Taisce	Civil Society
	Fridays for Future	Civil Society
	Leave no Trace Campaign	Civil Society
	Voice Ireland	Civil Society
	Department of Environmental Climate and Communications	Government
	Environmental Protection Agency	Government
	Geological Survey Ireland	Government
	National Parks and Wildlife Service	Government
	Office of Public Works	Government
	BIM Board Iascaigh Mara (Irish State Agency - Seafood)	Industry
	Enterprise Ireland	Industry
	Faite Ireland	Industry
	Irish Development Agency	Industry
	Irish Farmers Association (IFA)	Industry
Vilanova Stakeholders		
Level	Stakeholders	Category
Local	Josep Miro	Academic
	APMA (Environmental Group / Grupo Ecologista)	Civil Society
	Association of neighbours of the Barri de mar [Associo de veins del Barri de Mar]	Civil Society
	Consell de MEdi Ambient (environmental council)	Civil Society
	EDULIS	Civil Society
	Entities by Climate [Entitats pel Clima] (please specify)	Civil Society
	Federacion Asoc Vecinos	Civil Society
	Garaf Coopera	Civil Society

	Gava City Council (neighbouring municipality)	Government
	GEPEC (non-profit)	Civil Society
	La foixarda	Civil Society
	Co-work Neapolis	Industry
	Urbion ix	Industry
	ARBA litoral	Civil Society
	Vilanova Nautical Club [Club Nautic de Vilanova]	Civil Society
	Calafell City Council	Government
	Sitges City Council	Government
	Fishermen's Guild [Confradia de Pescadores]	Industry
Regional	ACA - Catalan Water Agency [Agencia Catalana del Agua], Gencat	Government
	CEM Sea Study Centers [Centros de estudio del mar]	Academic
	Obsea UPC Vilanova Underwater Observatory [Observatorio Submarino de la UPC de Vilanova]	Academic
	Barcelona Provincial Council [Diputació de Barcelona]	Government
	Catalan Climate Change Office [Oficina Catalana de Cambio Climatico (Gencat)]	Government
	Natural Park of Garraf [Parque Natural del Garraf]	Government
	Brins oportunitats	Industry
	Garraf Business Federation [Federacio empresaris Garraf]	Industry
	Sitges (neighbouring municipality)	Civil Society
	Sustainable Development Advisory Council of Catalonia (SADS), Generalitat de Catalunya	Government
	DG Coasts, Gencat	Government
	Natural and coastal environment service (Garraf County Council)	Government
	EURECAT (consultancy)	Industry
	SMART Catalonia	Industry
	DG Coast and Sea, Ministry for Ecological Transition, Spanish Government	Government

ANNEX 3 – OVERVIEW OF POLICIES RELEVANT TO CCLLS

Policies Relevant to CCLLS			Linkages to Technical Work Packages						
CCLL	Policy level	Policy name:	WP1	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8
Benidorm	National	Master Plan for Defense Against Floods in Marina Baja Region (Alicante)		X	X	X	X	X	
		Spanish Coastal Law	X		X				
		PINEC – National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate			X				
	Local	Benidorm Climate Change Adaptation Plan		X	X	X	X	X	
Dublin	National	National Climate Action Plan 2023		X	X	X	X	X	
		Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment Act) 2021		X	X	X	X	X	
	Local	Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council Climate Action Plan 2019-2024		X	X	X	X	X	
Gdansk	Regional	Adaptation Plan to Climate Change for Gdańsk till 2030 [Plan Adaptacji do Zmian Klimatu Miasta Gdańska do Roku 2030]		X	X	X	X	X	
		Diagnosis of Adaptation and Mitigation to Climate Change of the Gdańsk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area [Diagnoza Adaptacji i Mitygacji do Zmian Klimatu Obszaru Metropolitalnego Gdańsk-Gdynia-Sopot]		X	X	X	X	X	
Massa	National	Guidelines on Coastal Erosion - Establishment of the National Board on Coastal Erosion [Linee Guida Sull'erosione Costiera - Istituzione del Tavolo Nazionale Sull'erosione Costiera]	X	X		X			
	Regional	Masterplan of the Tuscany Region for the Protection of the Coast [Masterplan della Regione Toscana per la Tutela Della Costa]		X	X	X	X	X	
		Operational Document for the Coast of the Tuscany Region [Documento Operativo per la Costa della Regione Toscana]	X	X		X			
		Flood Risk Management Plan (PGR) of the Northern Apennine District Authority [Piano di Gestione Rischio Alluvioni (PGR) dell'Autorità di Distretto Appennino Settentrionale]	X	X					
Oarsoaldea	Regional	GEOEUSKADI: Online Spatial Environmental Data Platform for the Basque Country	X	X		X	X		X

		Evaluation of the Vulnerability and Risk of Basque Municipalities to Climate Change (2019)	X	X			X		X
		Guide for the Evaluation on the Effectiveness and Design of Nature-Based Solutions as Adaptation Measures to Climate Change (2018)		X		X			X
		Natural-Based Solutions for Climate Change Adaptation in Local Context of the Basque Country (2016) – Tecnalia-Neiker		X		X			X
		URBAN KLIMA 2015 (Naturklima) – LIFE Program of the European Commission		X	X	X	X		X
		Climate Change Strategy of the Basque Country (Basque Government)	X	X		X	X		X
		Climate Change Strategy of Gipuzkoa Province (Provincial Council of Gipuzkoa)	X	X		X	X		X
		Regional Strategic Plan 2017-2025 Oarsoaldea (2018) [Plan Estratégico Comarcal 2017-2025 Oarsoaldea (2018)]	X	X		X	X		X
		PINEC – National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate	X	X		X	X		
		Coastal and Fluvial Flooding Mapping and Nature-Based Solutions Guide (Basque Water Agency)	X	X		X	X		
	Local		Draft Landscape Action Plan for the Karrika Valley - Oiartzun (2016)		X		X		
		Special Plan for Organizing the Service Zone of Puerto de Pasaia (2018) Memoria + Environmental Studio		X		X			
		Errenteria: Climate Change Adaptation Plan	X	X		X	X		
Oeiras	Local	Municipality Action Plan to Climate and Energy (PAECO)			X				
		Municipality Civil Protection and Emergency Plan (PMEPC)			X				
Piran	National	National Energy and Climate Plan (NEPN)	X	X	X			X	
	Local	Municipal Spatial Plan [Občinski Prostorski Načrt] (draft)	X	X	X		X	X	
		Piran climate change adaptation plan (in development within the project) [Strategija za podnebno odpornost Pirana]	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Samsun	National	Climate Change Action Plan (2011-2023)		X	X	X	X	X	
		National Climate Change Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan (2011-2023)		X	X	X	X	X	
	Regional	Kızılırmak Basin Flood Management Plan		X	X				
		Kızılırmak Delta Management Plan 2019-2023		X	X				
		Kızılırmak Basin Management Plan		X	X				
	Local	Samsun Climate Change Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan		X	X				

		Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction Plan	X	X	X	X			
Sligo	National	National Climate Action Plan 23		X	X	X	X	X	
		Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment Act) 2021	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	Regional	Climate Action Regional Office - CARO - ASBN Sand Dune Protection and Restoration Project	X	X		X			
	Local	Sligo County Council Climate Adaptation Plan	X	X	X	X			X
		Coastal Erosion and Flood Risk Management (CEFRM) Study in Sligo Bay	X	X	X	X	X	X	
		Sligo County Council City Planning - Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS)		X			X		
Vilanova	National	Agenda 21			X				
		PINEC – National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan [Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima]	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	Regional	Maresme Climate Change Adaptation Plan (2021) [Pla d'Adaptació al Canvi Climàtic del Maresme (2021)]	X	X	X	X	X	X	
		Adaptation Plans for Garraf and Baix Llobrega [Plans d'adaptació del Garraf i Baix Llobregat]	X	X	X	X	X	X	
		Catalan Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change 2013-2020	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	Local	PAESC - Action Plan for Sustainable Energy and the Climate of Vila nova i la Geltrú	X	X	X	X	X	X	
		Climate Change Adaptation Plan (2018) – Vilanova i la Geltrú City Council	X	X	X	X	X	X	
		Climate Change Adaptation Plan for the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona	X	X	X	X	X	X	

ANNEX 4 – SCORE SYNERGIES WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND RELEVANT INITIATIVES

#	Name	Funding Programme	Coverage	URL	Type of activity
1	CoCliCo	H2020	Europe	https://coclicoservices.eu/	Cluster Adapt4Coast / Joint webinar / joint policy brief / joint poster
2	PROTECT	H2020	Europe	https://protect-slr.eu/	Cluster Adapt4Coast / Joint webinar / joint policy brief / joint poster
3	REST-COAST	H2020	Europe	https://rest-coast.eu/	Cluster Adapt4Coast / Joint webinar / joint policy brief / joint poster
4	Ocean&Climate Platform	Several members/ foundations	International	https://ocean-climate.org/en/taking-action-in-the-face-of-sea-level-rise-a-map-of-solutions-for-coastal-cities-and-territories/	Participation in a workshop on EbA in April 2024, SCORE CCLLs and tools featured on their platform, upcoming policy brief
5	Climate Adapt	EC/EEA	Europe	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/more-events/	Promotion of SCORE events (webinars, training school)
6	MIP4ADAPT	Horizon Europe	Europe	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/the-mission/about-mip4adapt	SCORE is part of the Thematic Working Group on Integrating Adaptation and Mitigation together with other projects. We participated in 3 synergy workshops organised by Mip4Adapt.
7	MAIA	H2020	Europe	https://maia-project.eu/	Video-interview of ATU presenting SCORE
8	ProClimate	Horizon Europe	Europe	https://pro-climate.eu/	Received funding for continuing living lab in Sligo
9	EmpowerUs	Horizon Europe	Europe	https://empowerus-project.eu/	Meetings with an Ireland living lab, invitation of a Norwegian living lab to the 1 st SCORE international workshop, co-produced paper on the relationship between Digital Tools and NBS
10	Eclipse	H2020	Europe	https://eclipse.eu/	Used research from SCORE/ATU for the EU Eclipse Expert Working Group report in March 2024

11	VITALISE	H2020	Europe	https://vitalise-project.eu/	Collaboration to develop a comparison for case-studies between the living lab in Sligo and VITALISE's living lab in the Basque Country. Findings presented at the VITALISE consortium meeting in Brussels in February 2024.
12	Science Foundation Ireland project	Irish government	Ireland	https://www.sfi.ie/	Received funding for a Science Foundation Ireland project where ATU is engaging/working local farmers in Ireland to build digital twin/use sensor technology developed in SCORE in to build sustainable and resilient farms.
13	Irish Ocean Literacy Network	Several members	Ireland	https://irishoceanliteracy.ie/	Participation in one of their group meetings in Galway in April 2023 to share experience of Sligo CCLL.
14	Pro-Coast	Horizon Europe	Europe	https://www.pro-coast.eu/en/c	Case study on the NBS dune management in Sligo as part of the EU Pro-Coast project, wherein ATU is building on the work done in SCORE on sand dune management in Sligo CCLL.
15	Climateurope2	Horizon Europe	Europe	https://climateurope2.eu/	Future participation in the Climateurope2 Festival in 2025 in Belgrade
16	CitiObs	Horizon Europe	Europe	https://citiobs.eu	Collaboration with the Dublin CCLL as a citizen observatory that will continue to collaborate in a mutual learning process. This means that some lessons learned or outputs from the Dublin CCLL can be transferred to other CCLLs in the future.
17	NatMed	PRIMA	Mediterranean	https://natmed-project.eu/	Participation in a workshop in June 2024 to share SCORE's best practices on EBA and discuss barriers and challenges. A second workshop will take place in January 2025.
18	iChange	H2020	Europe	https://ichange-project.eu/	A meeting was held to discuss potential collaboration, in particular in relation to the two projects' living labs in Dublin.

ANNEX 5 - OVERVIEW OF THE FORM TRACKING PARTNERS' COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIONS

	Communication channel (please select from the drop-down list)	Name/description of the communication activity	Leading partner	Date	Place	Purpose and expected impact	Target Audiences							Number of people reached	Outreach level (please select from the drop-down list)
							Academics and researchers	Cities	Industrial sector	Government bodies / policy makers	European and international networks / technology	EU projects	General public		
1	News in website	project approval	IHS	17.12.2020	IHS website	awareness	x					x		131 website visitors	International
2	News in website	Project kick off news	IHS	29.06.2021	IHS website	news dissemination increased awareness	x					x		327 website visitors	International
3	Social media	Project kick off news	IHS	14.07.2021	LinkedIn	news dissemination increased awareness	x					x	x	1,061 impressions LinkedIn	International
4	Social media	Project kick off news	IHS	14.07.2021	Twitter	news dissemination increased awareness	x					x	x	693 impressions Twitter	International
5	Social media	Project kick off news	EUR	16.07.2021	EUR LinkedIn group	news dissemination increased awareness	x					x	x	1700 followers Impressions: 192	International
6	Press kit	Press Release Template	ITS	16.07.2021	Link to press release template	news dissemination increased awareness	x	x				x	x		International
7	Press release	Project kick off news	ITS	20.07.2021	https://www.itsligo.ie/sligo-to-take-part-in-horizon-2020-project/	news dissemination increased awareness	x	x		x		x	x	TBC	International
8	Social media	Project kick off news	ITS	15.07.2021	LinkedIn and Twitter	awareness	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Twitter: Impressions 21,487. LinkedIn:	International
9				21/7/2021	LinkedIn and Twitter	awareness	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	TBC	International
10				20/7/2021	Press Release	awareness		x	x	x			x	Sent to all regional press in Northwest of Ireland	Regional
11	Podcast	Podcast with the project coordinator presenting the project	ITS	20/7/2021	Podcast - website and social media	awareness	x	x	x	x		x	x	TBC	European
12	Social media	Project kick off promotional post	ERINN	15/7/2021	Twitter	project promotion						x	x	TBC	European
13	Social media	Project kick off promotional post	ERINN	15/7/2021	LinkedIn	project promotion	x		x				x	Impression: 105	European
14	Social media	Project kick off promotional post	ERINN	14/7/2021	LinkedIn	project promotion	x		x				x	300	European
15	Press release	Project Press Release	ERINN		ERINN Website	project promotion	x		x			x	x	TBC	European

ANNEX 6 – SCORE KPI ANALYSIS

SCORE Communication and Dissemination plan

Dissemination or communication activity	Tool / Activity	When (and where, if relevant)	KPI	Target - M48	Target M36	Results - M36 - June 2024	Evaluation - M36				Partner(s) in charge	
							High (>100%)	Good (≤ 100%)	Moderate (≤ 75%)	Low (<50%)		
Events to be organised by the project partners	EBA Training Schools	2023, 2024, 2025	Number of training schools	30	20	20	>20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	ATU, UCD and CCLLs	
			Number of participants	30/session	30/session	55/session	>30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15		
	International technology workshops	2024, 2025	Number of workshop organised	2	1	1	>1	≤ 1	≤ 0	-	TBD	
			Number of participants	30-40/workshop	30-40/workshop	32	>30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15		
	Webinars	2024, 2025	Number of webinars	2	1	10	> 1	-	-	-	Euronovia	
Number of participants			40-50/webinar	40-50/webinar	64	> 40	≤ 40	≤ 30	< 20			
Final Info Day	M48		Number of participants	1000	0	N/A	-	-	-	Euronovia		
Citizen science activities and workshops in each CCLL	M6-M24		Number of activities	10	10	19	>10	≤ 10	≤ 7	< 5	ATU, UCD and CCLLs	
Participation in external events and conferences	Scientific conferences	Whole project duration	Number of conferences	10	8	24	> 8	≤ 8	≤ 6	< 4	All	
			Number of face to face contacts	100	75	4650	> 75	≤ 75	≤ 56	< 37		
	Exhibition fairs in technology and Open Innovation events	2024, 2025		Number of participation/exhibition	3	1	4	> 1	≤ 1	≤ 0	-	Euronovia
	Science popularization event	Whole project duration		Number of participation/exhibition	1	1	13	> 1	≤ 1	≤ 0	-	Euronovia, ALL
Website	M3-M6		Number of visits	1000/month	1000/month	2651/month	> 1000	≤ 1000	≤ 750	< 500	Euronovia	
			Number of news	2/month	72	100	> 72	≤ 72	≤ 54	< 36		
Flyer	M6		Number of flyers distributed	2000	1500	940	> 1500	≤ 1500	≤ 1125	< 750	Euronovia	
			Project videos/ Interview videos	M48	Number of videos	10	8	28	> 8	≤ 8	≤ 6	< 4
Number of views	50,000	37500			31965	> 37500	≤ 37500	≤ 28125	< 18750			
Massive Open Online Courses created from lectures and workshops	M36		Number of videos	30	30	16	> 30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	ERINN	
Final brochure	M48		Number of brochures distributed	2000	0	N/A	-	-	-	-	Euronovia	
LinkedIn page	Whole project duration		Number of followers	3000	2250	1258	> 2250	≤ 2250	≤ 1687	< 1125	All	
			Number of post	300	224	224	> 225	≤ 225	≤ 169	< 112		
Twitter account	Whole project duration		Number of followers	2000	1500	424	> 1500	≤ 1500	≤ 1125	< 750	All	
			Number of tweet	300	225	360	> 225	≤ 225	≤ 169	< 112		
Facebook page	Whole project duration		Number of followers	500	375	167	> 375	≤ 375	≤ 281	< 187	Euronovia, ERINN, ATU	
Instagram account	Whole project duration		Number of followers	500	375	251	> 375	≤ 375	≤ 281	< 187	CCLLs	
Final media press kit	At the end of the project			1	0	N/A	-	-	-	-	Euronovia	
Newsletter	Every 6 month, starting M6		Number of newsletter	8	5	5	> 5	≤ 5	≤ 4	< 3	Euronovia	
			Number of registered for updates	1000	750	568	> 750	≤ 750	≤ 562	< 375		
Press releases	M6, M30 and M42		Number of press releases	3	2	4	> 2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	Euronovia, ATU	
Article in specialized magazines	M24 and M36		Number of articles	2	2	3	> 2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	Euronovia, ALL	
Media coverage	Whole project duration		Number of external articles	100	75	91	> 75	≤ 75	≤ 56	< 37	All	
Decision-support guidelines for management of residual coastal risk (Wp6)			Number of set of guidelines produced	2	0	N/A	-	-	-	-	RED	
Policy recommendations to assist decision making in climate change adaptation at the local, national and EU level (Wp7)	M47				0	5	> 0	-	-	-	TERO	
Publications	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals	Whole project duration	Number of publications	30	23	35	> 23	≤ 23	≤ 17	< 11	All	
	Conference proceedings	Whole project duration	Number of conference proceedings	10	8	17	> 8	≤ 8	≤ 6	< 4	All	
	Special issue/special collection in a peer-reviewed journal	M48	Number of special issue	1	0	1	> 0	-	-	-	All	

ANNEX 7 – IMPACT READINESS LEVELS

IRL Level	SRL	TRL	Description of IRL
IRL 1: Conception	SRL 1	TRL 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation and/or identification of new knowledge awaiting validation through experimentation or peer-review • Research concepts or proposals generated following identification of stakeholder knowledge and evidence needs • Research knowledge requiring further definition to allow evaluation of the potential value chain • Anticipated research outputs require further development to enable progress along the value chain
		TRL 2	
		TRL 3	
IRL 2: Discovery	SRL2	TRL 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping and analysis of the stakeholders' landscape in order to grasp the value chain of the envisioned research outputs • Definition of knowledge outputs and strategic planning of knowledge transfer activities in order to create value • Successful communication of research to key target audiences at a medium/late stage of the project • Research agenda and process are co-designed with the potential stakeholders
	SRL3		
IRL 3: Engagement	SRL4	TRL 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of and/or participation in multi-stakeholder events with a common agenda • Successful outreach and systematic, planned involvement of various media channels • Scientific knowledge circulates along various channels in a stakeholder sensitive language • Early systematic exploration with specific stakeholders about requirements, barriers, opportunities for potential application
	SRL5		
	SRL6		
IRL 4: Implementation	SRL7	TRL 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The basis for research application is established through an iterative co-creation process • Consolidation and validation of 'actionable' results of research by stakeholders in practice • First implementation efforts can be demonstrated as single one-off events in a concrete societal context of application • Societal and political stakeholders are engaged in research evaluation and support learning feedback loops for researchers
	SRL8	TRL 7	
IRL 5: Uptake	SRL9	TRL 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrable uptake of research results and their advancement through policy influence and/or entering an enduring partnership with stakeholders • Sustainability of the multi-stakeholder process is planned for in previous stages and appears highly probable • Beneficial outcomes on target stakeholder groups are verifiable • Research leverages additional research funding and/or a change in the visibility and the positioning of the research organisation
IRL 6: Sustained Change		TRL 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrable scale-up and follow-ups both in regional and sectoral terms; emergence of spin-offs • The initiators/researchers are recognised as innovators and are consulted for advice for replication of good practices • Long term research contracts/further commissioned work with Departments/Agencies for sustained policy influence • The application of research in different contexts generates additional demand with funding organisations for further innovative research • Beneficial outcomes are measurable and introduce not merely a change in practice/policy but moreover a sustainable change in mindsets, culture and/or regulation

ANNEX 8 – KNOWLEDGE OUTPUT COLLECTION QUESTIONNAIRE

INTRODUCTION

SCORE employs a Knowledge Management and Transfer (definitions are explained in Annex 1) methodology to ensure that all relevant knowledge coming out of the project will be collected, transferred, and taken up by relevant users so we deliver impact* and create value from our activities.

The Knowledge Transfer methodology is detailed in full in the SCORE Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (PEDR).

As part of this process, SCORE partners are asked to complete this form to collect and understand Knowledge Outputs (Part 1. Knowledge Output Template).

KNOWLEDGE OUTPUT COLLECTION

All **SCORE** project Knowledge Output (KO)* will be captured in this internal questionnaire (Knowledge Output Questionnaire (KOQ) below), including their detailed descriptions of the KO. The information you provide here will us to assess whether a KO is of high potential to deliver impact and to get insight into what steps can be taken next to ensure your KO reach the users who can take them up.

In case of any questions, please contact ERINN Innovation (Rochelle@erinn.eu or casey@erinn.eu).

Knowledge Output Questionnaire (KOQ)

Short Title:

Please provide a short and concise title to describe your Knowledge Output

Owners: *Please provide the names & emails of the KO owner.*

Knowledge Output Description:

Try to give a comprehensive description, making the KO fully understandable to a non-expert. For example, what are the key characteristics of the KO? What is innovative about it? Please do include details on how it progresses beyond the current state-of-the-art / evidence base. Do you have a justifying body of evidence, or are there contradictory results?

Target Users / End User:

Please include as many sectors and target groups that you think would benefit from the application (uptake) of this Knowledge Output.

General examples: Academic, Research and Development community; Cities; Industrial Sectors; Government Bodies; European and International networks and technology clusters, etc.

Specific examples: environmental scientists, a local Chamber of Commerce, weather sensor manufacturers, insurance companies, city planning authorities, etc.

There can be more than one type of end-user and the above list is not exhaustive. Please be as specific as possible.

Potential Application & Impact:

Per identified end user (above), please identify possible applications of your KO. How can each End User use/apply your KO? What do you think could be the potential resulting impact of this KO once it has been transferred to and taken up by the Target Users/ End User(s)?

For example: Municipalities could apply this KO to develop warning systems that are adjusted for their local conditions. We expect there is a long timescale to application since municipal regulations are timely to adjust. Etc.

Current Status:

Please identify whether the Knowledge Output is finalised, is still being generated or whose status/future is unknown. Is the KO open or restricted access (if there are no plans to make publicly available now or in the future, please state Restricted Access; If possible, please provide a link to the KO (e.g., website address; Digital Object Identifier (DOI), scientific journal details, patent number, etc.).

Plans for dissemination and exploitation:

Do you have any plans to disseminate or exploit this KO? Please indicate past and current activities to reach your identified End User. Examples of such activities include publications, events and networking, collaborative research / researcher mobility, consultancy / training courses, licensing, new business / spin-offs, etc. Please include web addresses, reference material, project reports so further investigation can be carried out.

Other Information:

*Is there **anything else** you would like to tell us about your KO that you feel would help in our efforts to transfer it to the relevant End User(s) when deemed innovative and impactful?*

Please share a relevant deliverable report, publication or other information that would provide further information on the KO.